

MULTITuDE: Large-Scale Multilingual Machine-Generated Text Detection Benchmark

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Abstract

There is a lack of research into capabilities of recent LLMs to generate convincing text in languages other than English and into performance of detectors of machine-generated text in multilingual settings. This is also reflected in the available benchmarks which lack authentic texts in languages other than English and predominantly cover older generators. To fill this gap, we introduce MULTITuDE¹, a novel benchmarking dataset for multilingual machine-generated text detection comprising of 74,081 authentic and machine-generated texts in 11 languages (ar, ca, cs, de, en, es, nl, pt, ru, uk, and zh) generated by 8 multilingual LLMs. Using this benchmark, we compare the performance of zero-shot (statistical and black-box) and fine-tuned detectors. Considering the multilinguality, we evaluate 1) how these detectors generalize to unseen languages (linguistically similar as well as dissimilar) and unseen LLMs and 2) whether the detectors improve their performance when trained on multiple languages.

1 Introduction

Machine text generation has significantly progressed in the past few months thanks to a new generation of large language models (LLMs). First, it was the arrival of ChatGPT and later GPT-4 that made available inexpensive generation of text in a range of languages to millions of people with ChatGPT becoming the fastest growing consumer application in history. Second, the introduction of LLaMA (Touvron et al., 2023b) opened new

¹The dataset is available at Zenodo upon request for research purposes only: <https://zenodo.org/records/10013755>. The source code is available at: <https://github.com/kinit-sk/mgt-detection-benchmark>.

Figure 1: Train and Test languages from our dataset.

Train	Test: en	Test: non-en	Difference
en	0.9292	0.6903	↓ 25.7%

Table 1: Average F1-score of detectors fine-tuned on English train split of MULTITuDE dataset, then evaluated on English test split vs. non-English test languages. The ↓ 25.7% drop in performance calls attention to the need for **accurate multilingual MGT detectors**.

possibilities for researchers and practitioners for inexpensive fine-tuning of LLMs, consequently ushering fine-tuned models like Alpaca (Taori et al., 2023) or Vicuna (Chiang et al., 2023) mimicking the capabilities of much larger (and more expensive) ones such as ChatGPT. The defining characteristic of this new generation of LLMs is not only the increased quality of text generation, but also their *multilinguality*.

Due to the potential for misuse of machine-generated text (MGT) for influence operations (Goldstein et al., 2023), disinformation (Buchanan et al., 2021), spam or unethical authorship (Crothers et al., 2022a), there has been a substantial amount of research on the task of

machine-generated text detection (Jawahar et al., 2020; Stiff and Johansson, 2022; Uchendu et al., 2023a). Although GPT-3 was already capable of generating text in languages other than English and despite the availability of multilingual BLOOM (Scao et al., 2022), most of the prior works on this task have been (until very recently) still focusing on GPT-2 with English-only support or newer models like GPT-Neo (Gao et al., 2020), GPT-NeoX (Black et al., 2022) or GPT-J (Wang and Komatsuzaki, 2021) which were all trained on an English language only datasets.

Recently, first MGT datasets in languages other than English – AuTexTification for Spanish (Sarvazyan et al., 2023) and RuATD for Russian (Shamardina et al., 2022) – were made public for the detection task. There is also a dataset containing 5 languages (Chen et al., 2022), but this was obtained by the use of machine translation with human corrections, which renders it less useful for MGT detection benchmarking due to the potential noise. Thus, a dataset comprising authentic texts in multiple languages from a single domain (i.e., a text form, such as a news article or social media post) is still missing, hampering the comprehensive evaluation of detection methods in multilingual setting. At the same time, prior works have already shown that detectors fine-tuned on data in English fail to generalize to other languages (e.g. to German in case of Mitchell et al., 2023 showing a drop from 0.946 AUC ROC to 0.537), which is also confirmed by our results (see Table 1).

In this paper, we aim to address shortcomings of prior works and focus on the multilingual aspect of MGT detection task (a binary classification of a text to be human-written or machine-generated). Our main contributions are:

(1) We evaluate the **cross-language generalization** of fine-tuned detectors trained in monolingual vs. multilingual settings. More specifically, we evaluate how the detection methods fine-tuned to a specific language (monolingual) or to a set of training languages (multilingual) generalize to unseen languages. We observe strong influence of language family and script on generalization and clear benefits of multilingual fine-tuning.

(2) We provide a first comprehensive multilingual **benchmark of a range of state-of-the-art (SOTA) detection methods**, comparing the performance of *fine-tuned* detectors and their ability to

generalize to unseen LLMs to the performance of the *zero-shot* statistical detectors, such as Detect-GPT (Mitchell et al., 2023) or *black-box* methods, such as GPTZero.

(3) Finally, we introduce a **novel benchmarking dataset MULTITuDE** comprising of 74,081 texts (7,992 human-written and 66,089 machine-generated) in 11 languages (English, Spanish, Russian, Portuguese, Catalan, German, Dutch, Ukrainian, Czech, Arabic, and Chinese). The selected languages cover 4 different scripts and 5 language families (see Figure 1 for their geographic distribution). The included machine-generated texts were generated by 8 multilingual SOTA LLMs, namely GPT-3, ChatGPT, GPT-4, LLaMA-65B, Alpaca-LoRa-30B, Vicuna-13B, OPT-66B and OPT-IML-Max-1.3B covering various model sizes, architectures, and means of pre-training.

2 Related Work

Large Language Models (LLMs). They are language models with an unprecedented number of parameters trained on massive amounts of data, including models such as ChatGPT powered by GPT-3.5 or GPT-4 (OpenAI, 2023), OPT (Zhang et al., 2022), LLaMA (Touvron et al., 2023a), PaLM (Narang and Chowdhery, 2022), LaMDA (Collins and Ghahramani, 2021), BLOOM (Scao et al., 2022), Vicuna (Chiang et al., 2023), Alpaca (Taori et al., 2023), etc. The scale of LLMs has led to *emergent abilities*, observed only with these models, and solving of several non-trivial NLG and NLI (Natural Language Inference) tasks. Among the most impressive is the ability to generate authentic-looking human-like texts, nearly indistinguishable from human-written texts. Similarly impressive is the ability to generate coherent texts in languages other than English (Scao et al., 2022) as LLMs are mostly trained with over 50 languages. Because of these abilities, LLMs can be maliciously used, e.g. to generate misinformation (Shevlane et al., 2023). To combat LLM misuse, generated text detectors and benchmarks are required.

Datasets. Since transformer-based generative language models became ubiquitous in 2018, researchers have released datasets to address the new problem of *machine-generated text detection*. The most popular datasets are GPT-2² (Radford et al.,

²<https://github.com/openai/gpt-2-output-dataset>

Figure 2: MULTITuDE generation framework.

2019) and GROVER³ (Zellers et al., 2019) generated texts. However, as more Language Models (LM) got deployed, the need for more datasets from different LMs arose. Therefore Uchendu et al. (2020) released the first multi-generator (8 LMs) dataset in the news domain and Uchendu et al. (2021) released the first benchmark dataset (19 LMs) and environment for *machine-generated text detection*. Next, researchers released datasets for different domains - Academic papers (Liyanage et al., 2022; Rosati, 2022), News, Reddit posts & Recipes (Cutler et al., 2021), Amazon reviews (Adelani et al., 2020), multi-modal (i.e., images & texts) news articles (Tan et al., 2020), Tweets (Fagni et al., 2021), COVID-19 articles (Pagnoni et al., 2022), deepfake text in-the-wild (Pu et al., 2022a), gamification of MGT detection (Dugan et al., 2022), essays (Liu et al., 2023), prompt-generation (Anand et al., 2023; Peng et al., 2023), and multi-generator (27 LLMs) multi-domain (i.e., news, story, question, argument, scientific, etc.) data (Li et al., 2023).

However, the vast majority of these datasets are in English. A few researchers released non-English datasets in Russian (Shamardina et al., 2022), Chinese (Pu et al., 2022b), Iberian languages (Sarvazyan et al., 2023), and M4 which contains Russian, Chinese, Urdu, Indonesian, & Arabic languages (Wang et al., 2023). In light of the increasing number of multilingual LLMs, we generate the largest multilingual dataset for *machine-generated text detection* containing 11 languages.

Detection Methods. Prior works have shown that humans are already not capable of reliably distinguishing machine-generated from human-written text, with accuracy only slightly above random guessing (Uchendu et al., 2021) and even finding MGTs more trustworthy (Zellers et al., 2019). Thus, researchers have proposed a variety of automatic MGT detection methods. These include

stylo-metric-based, deep learning-based, statistics-based, and hybrid approaches (i.e., the ensemble of at least 2 approaches) (Uchendu et al., 2023a).

For stylo-metric-based detectors, researchers used linguistic features to capture the unique writing styles of the machine and human authors (Uchendu et al., 2020; Fröhling and Zubiaga, 2021; Kumarage et al., 2023). Due to the computational cost of extracting the linguistic features, researchers proposed a deep learning-based detector which involves fine-tuned and other variants of BERT (Zellers et al., 2019; Uchendu et al., 2021; Bakhtin et al., 2019; Liyanage et al., 2022; Rosati, 2022). However, deep learning models have a few limitations: (1) they are susceptible to adversarial perturbations (Gagiano et al., 2021; Crothers et al., 2022b; Wolff and Wolff, 2020) and (2) need a lot of labeled data to perform well. Thus, researchers proposed statistics-based techniques which are robust to adversarial perturbations and are unsupervised, requiring minimal data (Gehrmann et al., 2019; Mitchell et al., 2023; Gallé et al., 2021; Su et al., 2023). However, while these statistics-based detectors are more robust to perturbations than deep learning-based techniques, they still underperform deep learning-based models in terms of non-perturbed performance. Therefore, researchers combine statistics-based and deep learning-based techniques to gain adversarial robustness and high performance (Kushnareva et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022; Uchendu et al., 2023b; Zhong et al., 2020).

3 Benchmark Dataset

As suitable multilingual human-machine pair dataset containing authentic non-English texts and machine texts generated by SOTA text-generation models is not available, we have put together a new dataset, called MULTITuDE (benchmark dataset for MULTilingual machine Text DETection). Its human segment comprises texts in 11 languages (authentic news articles) from the MassiveSumm dataset (Varab and Schluter, 2021) (see Figure 2).

³https://github.com/rowanz/grover/tree/master/generation_examples

Language (Abbv)	Arabic (ar)	Catalan (ca)	Chinese (zh)	Czech (cs)	Dutch (nl)	English (en)	German (de)	Portuguese (pt)	Russian (ru)	Spanish (es)	Ukrainian (uk)	Total
Train	0	0	0	0	0	26969	0	0	8970	8910	0	44786
Test	2673	2691	2683	2689	2695	2491	2685	2673	2671	2676	2668	29295

Generator (Size)	alpaca-lora (30b)	gpt-3.5-turbo	gpt-4	llama (65b)	opt (66b)	opt-1ml-max (1.3b)	text-davinci-003	vicuna (13b)	Total Machine	Total Human
Train	5017	5023	5023	4998	4978	4956	5022	5013	40030	4756
Test	3273	3277	3277	3231	3251	3201	3275	3274	26059	3236

Table 2: Number of samples per language and per generator for train and test splits of the MULTITuDE dataset.

Titles of the selected articles have been used in the prompts for 8 language models to generate corresponding machine texts. The titles were split into train and test portion of the dataset, ensuring machine and human texts generated for the same title to be in the same split. The train split is used to fine-tune detectors in monolingual (a single training language) as well as multilingual (multiple training languages) manner; the test split of the dataset is used for evaluation of the detectors’ performances. Details regarding text generation and pre-processing of both, human and generated, texts can be found in Appendix B.

Language Selection. We have deliberately selected major languages from three different language families as our training languages – English (Germanic), Spanish (Romance), and Russian (Slavic). To see whether linguistic similarity influences the transferability of the detection, we have selected two genealogically related test languages for all of them – Dutch and German for English, Czech and Ukrainian for Russian, Portuguese and Catalan for Spanish. On top of that, we have also generated test data for linguistically completely unrelated Arabic (Semitic) and Mandarin Chinese (Sino-Tibetan).

Most of the languages use Latin script. Russian is the only training language that uses a different script - Cyrillic. We have deliberately selected Czech (Latin) and Ukrainian (Cyrillic) as its Slavic neighbours to see how the script affects the results. Arabic and Chinese use their own scripts. Overall, our selection of languages is still biased towards Indo-European languages and Latin script.

The selected languages are just representatives to see the effect and answer our research questions, while avoiding waste of resources (including more languages than necessary). Using the published source code, the study can easily be extended to other languages.

Generated Texts. The summarized statistics of the MULTITuDE dataset are provided in Table 2. The dataset includes approximately 1000 human texts for each training language along with the corresponding MGTs from each generation model. For each test language, 300 human texts with the same amount of MGTs per model are included.

The linguistic analysis (see Appendix B.4) confirmed that all used text-generation models have been able to generate texts in the requested language in more than 95% cases (based on the Fast-Text language detection) except for LLaMA 65B (still reaching over 85%), failing mostly in Arabic and Chinese texts which it was not pre-trained on. The numbers of unique sentences and words per text is comparable to human texts and the results from the subsequent experiments show that none of the LLMs generated texts that are especially easy to detect. Nevertheless, some artifacts in the machine texts may still be present, since such a detailed analysis of the generated texts was not performed.

4 Detection Methods

For the purpose of this benchmark, the MGT detection methods are divided into three categories. The first category includes the *black-box detectors* – zero-shot methods available either through web interface or API, providing only small amount or no information about the underlying model or method used for detection, typically provided as commercial paid services. The second category includes *statistical detectors* – zero-shot methods, relying on distributional differences between generated and human-written text. The third category includes the *fine-tuned detectors* – language-model-based methods, which require fine-tuning of the models for the MGT detection task. See Appendix C for a complete list and more details on detection methods used in the benchmark.

Black-Box Detectors. We examine popular commercial black-box detectors, specifically ZeroGPT⁴ and GPTZero⁵. Despite their wide use and support of non-English languages, the extent of their zero-shot multilingual and cross-lingual proficiency in detecting MGT remains unknown. The training methodologies, weight parameters, and the specific data used for these detectors remain undisclosed. We interacted with these detectors via a subscription-based API, enabling us to assess their performance on our multilingual dataset.

Statistical Detectors. We evaluate our dataset on all the current baseline and SOTA statistics-based detectors that had been previously shown to perform very well on English datasets (He et al., 2023; Mitchell et al., 2023), with all models (except Entropy) achieving over a 75% performance – Log-likelihood, Rank, Log-Rank, Entropy, GLTR Test-2, and DetectGPT. The main benefit of these techniques is that they require no training. Instead, they utilize the probability of each word in a piece of text to distinguish MGT from human-written texts. Typically, these statistics-based models use GPT-2 Medium to get the probability of the words, however, as we are evaluating with a multilingual dataset, we use mGPT, a multilingual GPT-based model. Further for DetectGPT, an additional model is used to generate perturbations to the original text, so we keep the default model for perturbation - T5 (Raffel et al., 2020).

Fine-Tuned Detectors. We have selected 7 most popular HuggingFace language models representing SOTA while taking multilinguality into account. In the experiments, these detector models have been fine-tuned on MGT detection task, taking various combinations of source languages and text generation models’ output contained in the MULTITuDE dataset. For each of the three training languages separately (English, Spanish, Russian), for all training languages combined, and for English language with 3-times more train samples, we have fine-tuned these detector models for each generator separately and for all generators data combined. It resulted in 45 fine-tuned versions of each detector model, resulting in 315 fine-tuned detection methods in total. Details regarding fine-tuning process can be found in Appendix D.

⁴<https://www.zerogpt.com>

⁵<https://gptzero.me/>

5 Experiments and Results

We evaluate various aspects of multilingual capabilities of the existing SOTA MGT detection methods. Mainly, we focus on detection capabilities in English and non-English languages. However, we also analyze cross-lingual relations and generalization capabilities of detectors fine-tuned on a specific language and specific MGT generator data.

Firstly, in Table 3, we provide comparison of detectors’ performance evaluated on the whole created multilingual MULTITuDE benchmark test data (i.e., the data balanced across 11 languages).

There are 315 fine-tuned detection methods, which is infeasible to show in a single table. For clarity, the table contains all evaluated black-box and statistical methods, but includes only the best-performing version of each base model of fine-tuned methods (i.e., only one fine-tuned version of XLM-RoBERTa is provided with information about language and generator LLM data used for training). Performance evaluation of all versions can be found in the associated GitHub repository. The results are ordered according to the achieved macro average F1-score (since the test data are highly imbalanced in terms of machine vs human classes). This metric is used in all experiments if not stated otherwise. In the table, we also show other standard performance metrics, such as weighted average of F1-score, Precision, Recall, Accuracy, and FPR (false positive rate) with FNR (false negative rate). These metrics are calculated based on a default classification threshold of 0.5. Such a threshold can be calibrated based on various aspects (such as minimizing FPR or maximizing Recall). Therefore, we also show AUC ROC (area under the curve of receiver operating characteristic), which is a threshold-independent metric calculated based on prediction probabilities rather than the predictions themselves. Unfortunately, due to missing prediction probabilities, it is available only for fine-tuned methods in our results. It must be noted that even when using optimal thresholds maximizing true positive rate and minimizing false positive rate, the key conclusions reported in this paper hold. We use the mentioned default threshold also when reporting results in the rest of this paper.

Based on the results, we can clearly see that fine-tuned methods outperform the others, when utilizing training data from all LLMs and all train languages (with two exceptions when fine-tuning on a single language performed better). We can

Detector Model	Method Category	Train Lang.	Train LLM	Macro avg F1-score	Weighted avg F1-score	Weighted avg Precision	Weighted avg Recall	Accuracy	FPR	FNR	AUC ROC
MDeBERTa-v3-base*	F	all	all	0.8480	0.9400	0.9403	0.9396	0.9396	0.2614	0.0354	0.9607
XLM-RoBERTa-large*	F	all	all	0.8240	0.9352	0.9357	0.9398	0.9398	0.4178	0.0158	0.9658
BERT-base-multilingual-cased*	F	all	all	0.7563	0.9073	0.9051	0.9104	0.9104	0.4781	0.0414	0.9188
RoBERTa-large-OpenAI-detector	F	all	all	0.7360	0.8933	0.8968	0.8904	0.8904	0.4308	0.0698	0.8645
mGPT*	F	ru	all	0.7219	0.8976	0.8941	0.9048	0.9048	0.5751	0.0356	0.8780
GPT-2 Medium	F	all	all	0.6646	0.8668	0.8682	0.8654	0.8654	0.5850	0.0787	0.7899
ELECTRA-large	F	en	all	0.5559	0.7952	0.8310	0.7684	0.7684	0.6530	0.1793	0.6053
Entropy + RandomForest*	S	N/A	N/A	0.4863	0.8335	0.8050	0.8729	0.8729	0.9756	0.0217	N/A
Rank*	S	N/A	N/A	0.4708	0.8375	0.7913	0.8895	0.8895	1.0000	0.0000	N/A
DetectGPT*	S	N/A	N/A	0.4708	0.8375	0.7913	0.8895	0.8895	1.0000	0.0000	N/A
Entropy*	S	N/A	N/A	0.4708	0.8375	0.7913	0.8895	0.8895	1.0000	0.0000	N/A
Log-likelihood*	S	N/A	N/A	0.4703	0.8368	0.7911	0.8880	0.8880	1.0000	0.0018	N/A
Log-Rank*	S	N/A	N/A	0.4702	0.8364	0.7911	0.8874	0.8874	1.0000	0.0025	N/A
GLTR Test-2 (Rank)*	S	N/A	N/A	0.4662	0.8282	0.7901	0.8707	0.8707	0.9991	0.0213	N/A
ZeroGPT*	B	N/A	N/A	0.4259	0.5559	0.8653	0.4744	0.4744	0.1681	0.5700	N/A
GPTZero	B	N/A	N/A	0.1605	0.1258	0.8636	0.1629	0.1629	0.0226	0.9383	N/A

Table 3: General performance of detection methods on the whole test split (all languages) of the MULTITuDE benchmark. Symbol * denotes detectors capable to handle multilingual text. Letters “B”, “S” and “F” denote the category of the detector as black-box, statistical and fine-tuned respectively. Due to space limitations, we only report the best-performing version of each base model in case of fine-tuned detectors.

also notice that zero-shot methods cannot clearly distinguish between human and machine texts generated by newest LLMs. However, this is evaluated across data of all test languages combined; the results can differ among languages. In the following subsections, we thus report the results per individual test languages.

5.1 Zero-Shot Setting

We aim to answer the following research question: *How are zero-shot (statistical and black-box) detectors capable of detecting MGT in multiple languages?* The objective is to see how well these detectors can detect machine text generated by the newest LLMs and whether these detectors are able to detect MGT in non-English languages.

To answer this question, we run these detectors on the test split of the MULTITuDE dataset and analyze their per-language performances.

(1) **Statistical detectors cannot cope with multilingual data.** From Table 3, we observe that these models achieve about 47% F1 score. This suggests that these statistics-based models are unable to perform well with this multilingual constraint. Also, we observe that Rank, Entropy, and DetectGPT achieve the same performance. This is because all 3 models only predict one class, the machine class. The MGTBench⁶ implementation of these methods, used in our experiments, uses a Logistic Regression classifier for binary predictions with default parameters. For the Entropy based method, we have also used a Random Forest classifier with hyperparameters optimized using Randomized Grid

⁶<https://github.com/xinleihe/MGTBench>

Search with 5-fold cross-validation and 1k of iterations (details regarding the optimized hyperparameters can be found in Appendix D.), achieving a slightly higher performance. Notably, we can see that such a model is predicting also a human class, although negligibly, meaning the method actually works. Finally, the low performance of these previously high-performing statistical models suggests the non-trivial nature of evaluating on a multilingual dataset.

(2) **Transferability to non-English languages cannot be properly evaluated.** It is due to the overall low performance (e.g., predicting a single class only) of the statistical and black-box detectors (even on English, as previously mentioned). Per-language results show that black-box detectors outperformed statistical detectors on English data, but their performance on other languages is the same or even worse (see Table 10 in Appendix E).

5.2 Monolingual Generalization

In this experiment, we aim to answer the following research question: *Do detectors fine-tuned in monolingual settings generalize to other languages?* Meaning, for example, will a detector fine-tuned on English data only perform well on Spanish? Is there a relation between how close languages are and how well the detectors generalize?

To answer this question, we use various versions of detectors, fine-tuned on individual language data. To better show language dependencies, we perform this experiment per each generator data separately. For example, the XLM-RoBERTa model is fine-tuned on GPT-4 machine data (plus human data)

Train Language	Test Language [mean (\pm confidence interval)]										
	ar	ca	cs	de	en	es	nl	pt	ru	uk	zh
en	0.5448 (± 0.07)	0.7335 (± 0.07)	0.6793 (± 0.06)	0.8104 (± 0.04)	0.9292 (± 0.02)	0.7018 (± 0.05)	0.7508 (± 0.07)	0.7362 (± 0.05)	0.7148 (± 0.05)	0.6746 (± 0.05)	0.5580 (± 0.05)
es	0.7857 (± 0.05)	0.8747 (± 0.03)	0.8016 (± 0.07)	0.8812 (± 0.03)	0.7322 (± 0.07)	0.9314 (± 0.02)	0.8143 (± 0.06)	0.8944 (± 0.03)	0.8375 (± 0.04)	0.8299 (± 0.05)	0.7216 (± 0.06)
ru	0.8487 (± 0.05)	0.6532 (± 0.07)	0.7924 (± 0.08)	0.7591 (± 0.06)	0.5760 (± 0.09)	0.6884 (± 0.07)	0.6915 (± 0.07)	0.6626 (± 0.07)	0.9522 (± 0.01)	0.9387 (± 0.02)	0.7294 (± 0.06)
all	0.8537 (± 0.04)	0.8977 (± 0.03)	0.8604 (± 0.07)	0.9073 (± 0.02)	0.9420 (± 0.02)	0.9372 (± 0.02)	0.8808 (± 0.04)	0.9253 (± 0.02)	0.9560 (± 0.01)	0.9374 (± 0.02)	0.7659 (± 0.04)
en3	0.5605 (± 0.09)	0.7484 (± 0.06)	0.7289 (± 0.07)	0.8244 (± 0.04)	0.9392 (± 0.03)	0.7156 (± 0.04)	0.7778 (± 0.07)	0.7508 (± 0.05)	0.7092 (± 0.06)	0.7118 (± 0.06)	0.6160 (± 0.05)

Table 4: Performance for the test languages based on various train language combinations. It shows the mean of all trained detectors with multilingual base models along with 95% confidence interval error bounds. The reported score is macro average F1-score.

from train split for English, and evaluated on GPT-4 machine data (plus human data) from test split for all languages separately (English, Spanish, etc.).

Table 4 shows the aggregated performance across all generators and all multilingual detectors (i.e., detectors having a multilingual base LM). We only use multilingual detectors here because they have the best performance, as the cross-lingual generalization capability of English-only models is worse (see Table 3). For each test language, we test whether the differences between train languages observed in Table 4 are statistically significant. To do this, we conduct repeated measures ANOVA tests for each test language: we use macro F1-score for a given test language as a dependent variable, the combinations of detectors and text generators as “subjects” and train language as an independent within-subjects variable. For all 11 test languages, the observed differences are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). We further conduct post hoc pairwise tests between pairs of train languages per each test language for a more in depth analysis. We also show how the performance for individual languages correlate in Table 5. For completeness, we also provide full results in Appendix E in Tables 11–13 for English, Spanish and Russian training language respectively.

There are several observations that can be made based on our results. (1) The results confirm that the **monolingually fine-tuned detectors are able to generalize to other languages**, although with some performance degradation. There are significant differences of performance achieved for individual test languages (ranging from 0.54 to 0.96).

(2) **Linguistic similarity matters.** The results indicate that the similarity between languages plays

a role in how they would generalize between each other. Spanish dominates both Catalan and Portuguese, similarly Russian works really well for Ukrainian. The correlations also clearly show that the performance of similar languages correlate with each other. Czech is the one exception from this trend, but it might be caused by the fact that it is both Slavic (more similar to Russian), but it also uses the Latin script (making it more similar to other Latin-using Indo-European languages).

(3) **English is an outlier language.** Overall it has low (but statistically significant) correlation with other related languages and it is the only language that has negative correlation with any other language. It is outperformed by Spanish in most cases, even for the languages from its own language family; observed differences in performance between using Spanish or English as a training language are statistically significant for both German and Dutch. At the same time, detectors trained on other training languages (Spanish and Russian) have unusually weak performance for English. We hypothesize that this is caused by the fact that English is often the most common language in the pre-training data for both the generators and the detectors, which might lead to different behavior (regarding cross-lingual capability) for this particular language (e.g., the perplexity might be lower).

(4) **Languages with Non-Latin scripts are correlated.** Even though Russian is completely unrelated to Arabic or Chinese, it has the best performance as a training language (although the differences in performance when using Russian or Spanish as a training language are not statistically significant). The Non-Latin script languages seem to correlate well with each other. This might indi-

Languages	Germanic Languages			Romance Languages			Slavic Languages			Others	
	en	de	nl	es	pt	ca	cs	ru	uk	ar	zh
en	1.0000	0.5420	0.5551	0.3794	0.4960	0.4237	-0.16 (n.s.)	-0.3235	-0.4988	-0.2672	-0.00 (n.s.)
de	0.5420	1.0000	0.6006	0.7657	0.8022	0.6491	0.2176	0.20 (n.s.)	0.08 (n.s.)	0.20 (n.s.)	0.17 (n.s.)
nl	0.5551	0.6006	1.0000	0.5585	0.6905	0.8342	0.06 (n.s.)	0.2403	0.05 (n.s.)	0.3516	0.4694
es	0.3794	0.7657	0.5585	1.0000	0.9317	0.7331	0.16 (n.s.)	0.18 (n.s.)	0.12 (n.s.)	0.2989	0.2015
pt	0.4960	0.8022	0.6905	0.9317	1.0000	0.8251	0.09 (n.s.)	0.13 (n.s.)	0.05 (n.s.)	0.2483	0.19 (n.s.)
ca	0.4237	0.6491	0.8342	0.7331	0.8251	1.0000	0.15 (n.s.)	0.2103	0.08 (n.s.)	0.3345	0.3160
cs	-0.16 (n.s.)	0.2176	0.06 (n.s.)	0.16 (n.s.)	0.09 (n.s.)	0.15 (n.s.)	1.0000	0.3690	0.4489	0.4264	0.4500
ru	-0.3235	0.20 (n.s.)	0.2403	0.18 (n.s.)	0.13 (n.s.)	0.2103	0.3690	1.0000	0.8606	0.7378	0.4463
uk	-0.4988	0.08 (n.s.)	0.05 (n.s.)	0.12 (n.s.)	0.05 (n.s.)	0.08 (n.s.)	0.4489	0.8606	1.0000	0.7398	0.4664
ar	-0.2672	0.20 (n.s.)	0.3516	0.2989	0.2483	0.3345	0.4264	0.7378	0.7398	1.0000	0.7249
zh	-0.00 (n.s.)	0.17 (n.s.)	0.4694	0.2015	0.19 (n.s.)	0.3160	0.4500	0.4463	0.4664	0.7249	1.0000
	Latin Script						Non-Latin Script				

Table 5: The correlations between the macro average F1-score performance of the test languages calculated based on the results from multilingual detectors (i.e., having a multilingual base LM). The results that are not statistically significant are marked by (n.s.).

cate that the models behave differently for the Latin script (which is, again, by far the most common) than for other scripts.

5.3 Multilingual Generalization

In this experiment, we aim to answer the following research question: *Do detectors fine-tuned in multilingual settings generalize better to unseen languages than monolingually fine-tuned ones?* The objective is to see whether it is beneficial to train detectors on multilingual rather than on monolingual data in regard to transferability to other languages.

For the purpose of this experiment, we fine-tune the detectors by using the train samples of all three languages combined. The train set consists of 1k MGTs and 1k human texts for each train language (this train set is denoted as *all* in the results). The evaluation is also done per each LLM separately. In order to see whether the performance is not strictly based on a higher number of train samples, we also fine-tune the detectors with a comparable amount of English-only data, i.e., also approximately 6k train samples (this train set is denoted *en3*). The mean results are provided in bottom two rows of Table 4, analogously to the previous experiment. For completeness, the full results of each detector per each LLM-generated data are provided in Appendix E in Tables 14 and 15.

The multilingually fine-tuned detectors perform better on unseen languages than the monolingually fine-tuned ones. The observed differences in performance between using all three train languages (*all*) and all other train setups are statistically significant in case of Czech, German, Dutch and Portuguese. For all other test languages, the multilingually fine-tuned detectors also perform better (with the sole exception of the Ukrainian language where the detectors trained on Russian

slightly outperform the ones trained on *all*), but the differences to the best monolingually fine-tuned detectors are not statistically significant. The reason for a better performance of the multilingually fine-tuned detectors may be a higher amount of training samples. Indeed, when we look at the results of detectors fine-tuned with the *en3* train set, they achieve a slightly (but mostly not statistically significantly) better performance in almost all cases compared to the original English fine-tuned detectors (performing almost the same as multilingually fine-tuned detectors on English). However, the generalization to other languages is still significantly better in multilingually fine-tuned detectors (*en3* having a minimum at 0.56 for Arabic vs. *all* having a minimum at 0.77 for Chinese). Thus, regarding transferability to other languages, the detectors fine-tuned in multilingual manner seem stronger (for detectors with multilingual base models as well as for the ones with monolingual base models; see Appendix E for the latter).

5.4 Cross-Generator Generalization

We also aim to answer the research question: *How do fine-tuned detectors trained on data from a single LLM perform in detecting MGT by different LLMs?* Analogously to cross-lingual evaluation in Section 5.2, the objective of this experiment is to scrutinize the cross-generalizability among distinct LLMs by each individual detector fine-tuned on data from a single LLM.

Table 6 shows the correlation in the performance of each individual LLM. Comprehensive results (i.e., all the macro F1-scores, mean, and standard deviation separated per each language) are provided in Appendix E in Tables 16–20.

LLM similarity matters. We discern two distinct groups, namely, **Group 1**: text-davinci-003,

	text-davinci-003	gpt-3.5-turbo	gpt-4	alpaca-lora-30b	vicuna-13b	llama-65b	opt-66b	opt-impl-max-1.3b
text-davinci-003	1.0000	0.9585	0.9005	0.9357	0.9381	-0.4537	-0.3444	-0.3574
gpt-3.5-turbo	0.9585	1.0000	0.9712	0.8562	0.9056	-0.5131	-0.4805	-0.4872
gpt-4	0.9005	0.9712	1.0000	0.7781	0.8786	-0.4868	-0.4779	-0.5218
alpaca-lora-30b	0.9357	0.8562	0.7781	1.0000	0.9268	-0.2870	-0.1261	-0.1226
vicuna-13b	0.9381	0.9056	0.8786	0.9268	1.0000	-0.2221	-0.1273	-0.1632
llama-65b	-0.4537	-0.5131	-0.4868	-0.2870	-0.2221	1.0000	0.7721	0.6990
opt-66b	-0.3444	-0.4805	-0.4779	-0.1261	-0.1273	0.7721	1.0000	0.9011
opt-impl-max-1.3b	-0.3574	-0.4872	-0.5218	-0.1226	-0.1632	0.6990	0.9011	1.0000

Table 6: The correlations between the macro average F1-score performance of the cross-generator. All the presented results are statistically significant.

gpt-3.5-turbo, gpt-4, alpaca-lora-30b, and vicuna-13b, and **Group 2**: llama-65b, opt-66b, and opt-impl-max-1.3b. These groups have positive and negative correlations with each other. Group 1 primarily consists of models developed by OpenAI such as text-davinci-003, gpt-3.5-turbo, and gpt-4. Alpaca is a derivative fine-tuned model from a LLaMA 7B model on 52K instruction-following demonstrations generated from text-davinci-003 (Taori et al., 2023), while Vicuna is also fine-tuned with 70K user-shared ChatGPT conversations and achieves 92 % ChatGPT (i.e., gpt-3.5-turbo) quality (Chiang et al., 2023). Hence, we consider these as OpenAI-based models. On the other hand, Group 2 encompasses models developed and released by Meta AI, hence recognized as Meta-based models. The LLM architectures within each group are similar, which may cause the similar fine-tuned performance on the dataset and this observed phenomenon.

6 Discussion

Multilingual fine-tuned detectors perform the best. Fine-tuning multilingual LMs is the best approach based on our results, outperforming both English LMs and statistical methods. They have better ability to generalize to other unseen languages unmatched by the other methods. Still, their performance on the MULTITuDE dataset is far from perfect and the best model (MDeBERTa-v3-base) achieved Macro F1 score of 0.85. As such, they can not be used to reliably detect MGTs.

Linguistic similarity matters. Our results show that the linguistic similarity between the languages influence how well they generalize to each other and how much the performance for the languages correlate. The typology of the languages, but also the script they use are important. Multilingual MGT detectors should be trained and tested with a diverse set of languages to ensure the inclusivity of their performance. Yet, the practical development is often hindered by the fact that different LMs

(used both as generators and detectors) support different sets of languages to different extent, making it hard to create one-model-fits-all solutions.

English is an inappropriate default. As mentioned previously, the performance on the English language is an outlier and the models do not generalize to other languages that well from this language. English is often used as the *de facto* default language for many NLP use cases, including using it as a source language for crosslingual learning. This should be reconsidered for multilingual MGT detection.

7 Conclusion

In the paper, we provide the first comprehensive benchmark of black-box, statistical and fine-tuned machine-generated text detection methods in multilingual settings using our novel MULTITuDE dataset, covering 11 languages and 8 SOTA LLMs. Our results show that most currently available black-box methods do not work in multilingual settings and that the statistical approaches lag behind the fine-tuned ones. We also show that fine-tuning models in a multilingual manner (i.e., train data in multiple languages) results in better performance of detectors for unseen languages compared to monolingual fine-tuning. The generalization is strongly affected by language script as well as language family branches of the train and test languages. Also, English seems a particularly inappropriate choice of a training language if one aims for generalization of machine-generated text detection to non-English languages. This further emphasizes the importance of creating multilingual benchmarks for machine-generated text detection such as MULTITuDE. As a future work, we plan to extend it with a more diverse set of languages (in terms of scripts and language families) and with texts from other domains, especially social media.

Limitations

Language Selection. Our work is limited by the final selection of 3 training and 11 testing languages. This already allowed us to discover that there are interesting linguistic properties in the detector methods, but based on our work we still can not tell how they would behave with all the other languages. Non-European languages especially are still a blind spot in our evaluation.

Limited Amount of Training Data. Another limitation, closely related to the previous one is the fact, that the amount of data we use for benchmarking is limited. Apart from using different languages, the data could also be expanded by different domains, writing styles, etc. The amount of training data we use is also limited (several thousand samples), and simply extending the existing data could also yield additional improvements.

Limited Selection of Generative Language Models. In the end, we have selected and experimented with 8 generative language models, which are capable of generating multilingual content. It is hard to ascertain how generalizable the results are for all the other language models that are being or will be developed in future with different training data and different training regimes.

Ethics Statement

As a part of this paper, we introduce the MULTITuDE dataset consisting of human-written and machine-generated texts. The human-written texts are news articles collected in the MassiveSumm dataset (Varab and Schluter, 2021). The MassiveSumm dataset does not specify a license under which they publish the data as its public version only contains a list of URLs and a software package for their downloading and processing. Thus, we can assume that the news articles are protected by copyright, which, however, allows their use for non-commercial research such as our work. Although most of the LLMs we used were hosted at our premises, we also used OpenAI API. As a part of the prompts, we were sending headlines of the news articles to the API; these, however, are not used by the OpenAI to train or improve their models (which would constitute a commercial use) and they are retained for a maximum duration of 30 days, after which they are deleted.⁷

⁷<https://openai.com/policies/api-data-usage-policies>

Regarding the used LLMs, we made sure to follow their terms of use as well. LLaMA models (and their variants Alpaca and Vicuna) are licensed for non-commercial use only.⁸ Additionally, outputs of OpenAI services cannot be used to “develop models that compete with OpenAI.”⁹ Respecting these limitations, we publish the MULTITuDE dataset containing both the human-written texts with attribution (original source) and the machine-generated texts only for *non-commercial research purposes*.

Intended Use. The collected dataset is primarily intended to be used for research of multilingual machine-generated text detection. We used it for binary classification, but it could also be employed for multi-class classification (i.e., *authorship attribution* as defined in Uchendu et al., 2021, 2023a). We also publish the code for analysis and reproduction of our results including the training (fine-tuning) of the detection methods. These are also intended for research purposes only. They are not intended (in their current form) to be used in actual deployment where they would be automatically classifying the texts as human-written or machine-generated.

Failure Modes. As already noted in limitations, the fine-tuned detectors, while showing promising performance in our experiments, might fail when used on unseen languages, texts from different domains or writing styles. Additionally, they can fail to generalize to other unknown LLMs, decoding strategies or obfuscation efforts. The potential harms are not only from false negatives (i.e., failing to detect machine-generated texts), but also (and potentially even more so) from false positives (i.e., falsely flagging a text as being machine-generated while it was in fact human-written). It is also worth noting that there are many non-malicious uses of machine-generated texts (e.g., proofing, translation, etc.), which needs to be considered before any use of the detection methods trained on our collected dataset for purposes beyond research.

Biases. Although we selected languages from different language families and with different scripts (see Section 3), the dataset is still biased towards Indo-European languages and Latin script. Because of the nature of the training data which consists of news articles written in a standardized form

⁸https://github.com/facebookresearch/llama/blob/main/MODEL_CARD.md

⁹<https://openai.com/policies/terms-of-use>

of each included language, detectors fine-tuned on the dataset might be biased with respect to use of dialects, slang or code-switching which could potentially harm individuals from some ethnic groups or social origins.

Misuse Potential. We believe that there is only a limited possibility of misuse of our dataset. First, the dataset is published for research purposes only. Second, the machine-generated texts, although inauthentic and most likely false, should not cover any sensitive topics. Also, the used prompts to LLMs were to generate news articles given a headline; we did not prompt the LLMs to intentionally generate disinformation. So their potential harm and impact in case of misuse is limited.

Collecting Data from Users. The collection and processing of the dataset did not include any crowd workers or any other annotators. We do not intentionally collect or store any personal data as a part of this research. Some personal data (e.g., names) might be generated by the LLMs, but we can assume these to be mostly public figures that could have appeared in the training data of LLMs.

Potential Harm to Vulnerable Populations. To the best of our knowledge, the dataset does not cover any sensitive topics beyond what is normally covered in the news. As already noted in *Biases*, the dataset does not include texts in different writing styles, dialects or slang which can be used by marginalized populations and the detectors fine-tuned on the dataset could thus fail in such cases.

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A Computational Resources

For the purpose of data pre-processing and results analysis, we have used Google Colab¹⁰ without GPU acceleration, leaving thus only small carbon footprint on the environment. For the machine text generation, we have used multiple resources. For the OpenAI LLMs, we have used OpenAI API, requiring no GPU acceleration on our side. For LLaMA 65B, Alpaca LoRa 30B, and OPT 66B models, we have used 1× A100 40GB GPU (4× A100 for >60B models), with a cumulative run-time of approximately 32 GPU-days. For Vicuna 13B and OPT-IML 1.3B models, we have used 1× NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 24GB GPU, with a cumulative run-time of approximately 8.5 GPU-days. Regarding detectors fine-tuning, we have used 1× NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 24GB GPU, with a cumulative run-time of approximately 11.3 GPU-days. For running black-box detectors, we have also used Google Colab without GPU acceleration. For running statistical methods requiring a base LLM (i.e., mGPT), we have used 1 × A100 40GB GPU on an a2-highgpu-1g machine type.

B Data Pre-processing

For MULTITuDE dataset creation, we have used human texts from the original articles included in the MassiveSumm¹¹ (Varab and Schluter, 2021) dataset. We have used on-request author-provided processed data as well as CommonCrawl based links published in the GitHub repository. Both sources result in per-language datasets (split into files according to languages).

B.1 Human-Text Pre-processing

We have selected 3 languages for training (detectors fine-tuning) and 8 more for testing (11 languages in total). For each of the selected languages, we have taken the first 50,000 samples (if available for that language) from each data source. It resulted up to 100,000 samples per language.

The texts of these samples were stripped, meaning that white-space characters from beginning and end of texts are removed. Out of these samples, we have dropped samples with missing values and duplicated samples. Then, we have dropped samples that contained texts with 5 or less words (where the “word” is represented as a white-space delimited substring).

¹⁰<https://colab.research.google.com/>

¹¹<https://github.com/danielvarab/massive-summ>

Language	Original	N/A & Duplicates Removed	Min Textsize Applied	Language Checked
ar	73990	67351	67267	56140
ca	804	804	804	569
cs	97136	86507	84797	59039
de	69300	69127	69099	54914
en	42050	35023	34611	8812
es	99594	92484	91569	38254
nl	1797	1797	1797	1489
pt	95444	90209	90020	38857
ru	95797	88743	88304	51938
uk	100000	92868	90924	39844
zh	92698	81812	56678	8875
All	768610	706725	675870	358731

Table 7: Overview of the amount of language samples from the MassiveSumm dataset remaining after each pre-processing step.

The MassiveSumm per-language datasets contained texts in other languages, meaning that some texts were in different languages than the intended language according to the file (identified in the filename). Therefore, we have performed language detection of samples and dropped those that did not match. For language detection, we have used a combination of FastText¹² (Joulin et al., 2017) and polyglot¹³ tools. We have taken the language predictions into account only if the probability score (“confidence”) was at least 0.9. We have performed such detection separately using the title and the first sentence of the text for a given sample, resulting in 4 predictions. Out of these a majority voting was used to give a final detection result.

Table 7 provides amounts of texts per language available after each of the above mentioned pre-processing step.

After pre-processing, we have pseudo-randomly sub-sampled the English data to 3300 samples, Spanish and Russian to 1300 samples, and others to 300 samples. 300 samples of each language are then used for test split, while the remaining ones are in train split of the dataset.

The selected numbers of samples are based on our preliminary study using the existing datasets: TuringBench English data (Uchendu et al., 2021), AuTextification Spanish data (Sarvazyan et al., 2023), and RuATD Russian data (Shamardina et al., 2022). We have extensively experimented and chose a minimal number of samples needed to fine-tune the detectors and properly evaluate them. Specifically, we have compared the performances using the selected smaller amount of samples (500, 600, 1000, 1500 human samples where available)

¹²<https://github.com/facebookresearch/fastText/>

¹³<https://github.com/aboSamoor/polyglot>

and all samples available (5000 for English, 1150 for Spanish, 2450 for Russian). These experiments resulted in 1k human samples and 1k samples per text-generator required for training, with a negligible drop in the performance of fine-tuned detectors (i.e., within 5 %). For testing, 300 texts per class shown to be enough, giving the same detector performance values as using all the available samples. In addition, since we are experimenting with smaller number of samples in train sets, we have provided 3k human texts for English train data to ensure that the performance effect is not simply due to a higher number of train samples in case of multilingually fine-tuned detectors.

B.2 Machine Text Generation

Titles (i.e., headlines) of the human-text samples have been used in prompts to generate corresponding machine texts by multiple large language models. For instruction-following models, an instruction-based prompt has been used (a universal prompt in English instructing to generate text in a target language, corresponding to the title in the target language), pure title in the others. The instruction-based prompt was used in the form as follows (where `language_name` and `headline` are variables inserting strings specifying language and title of an individual text sample):

```
You are a multilingual
journalist.\n\nTask: Write a news
article in {language_name} for the
following headline: "{headline}".
Leave out the instructions, return just the
text of the article.\n\nOutput:
```

Settings for the text generation include minimal length of generated text set to 200 tokens, maximal length of generated text set to 512 tokens, number of return sequences set to 1, sampling activated with beams number of 1, top_k of 50, and top_p of 0.95. For models available via OpenAI API, we have set only maximal number of tokens to 512 and top_p to 0.95.

B.3 Generated-Text Pre-processing

Pre-processing of the generated texts included text stripping (i.e., white-space characters from beginning and end of texts are removed), removal of prompts from the generated text (both title and instruction-based prompt), removal of unfinished sentence from the end of the text (if more sentences are present). In order to achieve similar text

Generator	Language	Empty	Short	WC	WC	US	US	UW	UW
	Match	Text	Text	mean	std	mean	std	mean	std
text-davinci-003	100.00	0	3	136.57	76.32	1.00	0.00	0.67	0.14
gpt-3.5-turbo	99.98	0	0	152.22	76.85	1.00	0.00	0.65	0.13
gpt-4	100.00	0	0	208.86	121.91	1.00	0.00	0.64	0.13
alpaca-lora-30b	98.99	0	10	115.78	59.27	1.00	0.02	0.68	0.12
vicuna-13b	97.11	0	12	155.40	80.64	1.00	0.02	0.62	0.14
llama-65b	85.71	0	71	150.79	87.76	0.98	0.07	0.59	0.15
opt-66b	96.47	0	71	152.26	103.62	1.00	0.03	0.67	0.15
opt-impl-max-1.3b	95.20	7	143	154.04	112.30	0.99	0.08	0.61	0.19
human	99.89	0	0	136.82	78.16	1.00	0.02	0.69	0.12

Table 8: Statistics of the machine-generated texts. Mean and standard deviation of ratios are provided, where WC refers to the word count, US refers to the unique sentences, and UW refers to the unique words.

lengths distribution between human and machine texts, each machine text is shortened if the corresponding human text (title of which was used in the prompt) is shorter. Similarly, the human texts are shortened to a mean value of lengths of the corresponding machine texts. Shortening occurs only if the difference between the corresponding machine and human texts lengths is greater than 5 words and if more than one sentence is present. Shortening is performed by removal of the last sentence from the longer text until the condition is met. Such texts are then processed by the FastText full-text language detection, and language mismatch is analyzed (see the next subsection).

After the initial analysis of the generated texts, we have noticed multiple prompts were duplicated. In order to preserve consistency, we have moved all texts generated for the duplicated prompts to the same (train) split of the dataset. The intuition is to avoid having the texts generated for the same prompt in both splits. We have then dropped generated samples with 5 or less words and dropped text duplicates, ensuring no text sample has multiple labels. Fortunately, even after occurrence of duplicated texts and their removal from the final dataset, the numbers of samples are not significantly reduced. The smallest number in the train split is the number of human Spanish samples having 937 unique texts (out of intended 1000). The smallest number in the test split is the number of llama-65b English samples having 275 unique texts (out of intended 300). Thus, the numbers of samples for each text-generation language model and for each language are still well balanced.

B.4 Linguistic Analysis of the Generated Text

The statistics of the analyzed generated texts per language model are provided in Table 8. For Chi-

nese word count, polyglot tool was utilized. For other languages, white-space separated substrings are counted. The *Empty Text* column contains number of samples with no new text generated (i.e., returned only the provided prompt or no text at all). The *Short Text* column represents the number of generated texts with 5 or less words. As the table indicates, the llama-65b model performed worst in generating texts in multiple languages. But it still had more than 85% accuracy regarding language match (i.e., the language of the generated text is the same as the one queried by the prompt). We must also take into account the fact that FastText language identification is not error-free (i.e., misclassification can occur). As expected, deeper analysis revealed that llama-65b model have missed mostly Chinese and Arabic languages (202 and 140 mismatched samples, respectively), since these were not used in the model training.

C Description of Detection Methods

Table 9 shows descriptions of all detection methods used in the benchmark. The base models for the detection methods have been carefully selected with respect to the state-of-the-art and the limited experimentation resources. We have primarily used multilingual base models (XLM-RoBERTa, BERT-multilingual, mGPT, and MDeBERTa) that are publicly available and belong to the SOTA multilingual pre-trained models used for a wide range of downstream tasks. Besides these, we have also used English-only pretrained models that have been commonly used as detectors in previous studies (Uchendu et al., 2021; Zhong et al., 2020). We used these to see how they would perform on non-English language datasets. In this group, there were RoBERTa-large-OpenAI-detector, GPT2, and ELECTRA.

Detector	Category	Description
ZeroGPT	Black-box	ZeroGPT service uses a series of complex and deep algorithms to analyze the text, presented with an accuracy rate of text detection up to 98%, claiming to detect AI text output in all the available languages. https://www.zerogpt.com
GPTZero	Black-box	GPTZero model can detect AI-generated and human-written text across the sentence, paragraph, and document levels. Training on a mixed corpus of AI and human English writings, it can accurately classify 85% of AI and 99% of human texts using a 0.65 threshold. To reduce false positives, a 0.65 or higher threshold is advised. https://gptzero.me/
Log-likelihood (Solaiman et al., 2019)	Statistical	Given a text, this method calculates the average word log probability of each word. The log probability is extracted from a language model (i.e., mGPT (Shliazhko et al., 2022)).
Rank (Gehrmann et al., 2019)	Statistical	Similar to Log-likelihood, given each word in a text, using the context, this method calculates the absolute rank of the word. Next, we calculate the average rank score of each word.
Log-Rank (Mitchell et al., 2023)	Statistical	Similar to the Rank metric, Log-Rank takes the log probability of the Rank score for each word.
Entropy (Mitchell et al., 2023)	Statistical	Similar to the Rank score, Entropy is calculated by obtaining the entropy score of each word, given its context (i.e., previous words), and calculating the average of the final scores.
GLTR (Gehrmann et al., 2019)	Test-2 (Rank) Statistical	GLTR uses 3 tests to calculate scores used to distinguish machine-generated text from human-written text. However, following the same procedure used by (He et al., 2023), we only use the 2nd test - calculating the rank of the fraction of words within the top-10, top-100, top-1000, > top-1000 probable words.
DetectGPT (Mitchell et al., 2023)	Statistical	DetectGPT perturbs the text and compares the changes between the original and the perturbed text. This comparison is done by calculating the log probability of the original vs. perturbed texts. The hypothesis is that machine-generated text tends to lie in the negative log probability curve, while human-written text will have a higher or lower probability than the perturbed text.
RoBERTa-large-OpenAI-detector ¹⁴ (Solaiman et al., 2019)	Fine-tuned	This is a sequence classifier based on RoBERTa Large, fine-tuned to distinguish between GPT-2 generated text and WebText.
GPT-2 Medium (Radford et al., 2019)	Fine-tuned	GPT-2 Medium ¹⁵ is a transformer-based autoregressive language model, pre-trained on English language.
XLNet-RoBERTa-large (Conneau et al., 2019)	Fine-tuned	XLNet-RoBERTa ¹⁶ is a pre-trained on 2.5TB of filtered CommonCrawl data containing 100 languages.
BERT-base-multilingual-cased (Devlin et al., 2018)	Fine-tuned	Multilingual version of BERT ¹⁷ is a masked language model pre-trained on the top 104 languages with the largest Wikipedia.
mDeBERTa-v3-base (He et al., 2021a)	Fine-tuned	mDeBERTa ¹⁸ is a multilingual version of DeBERTa (He et al., 2021b) trained with CC100 data containing 100 languages.
ELECTRA-large (Clark et al., 2020)	Fine-tuned	ELECTRA ¹⁹ is a language model pre-trained as a discriminator rather than a generator.
mGPT (Shliazhko et al., 2022)	Fine-tuned	mGPT ²⁰ is a multilingual autoregressive model using GPT-3 architecture, trained on 61 languages from 25 language families using Wikipedia and Colossal Clean Crawled Corpus.

Table 9: A detailed list of all detection methods used in this benchmark together with their descriptions.

D Model Parameters

For the purpose of fine-tuning language models for machine-generated text detection task, we have used Trainer²¹ API of the transformers library²² for PyTorch framework. We have used maximum number of 10 epochs with early-stopping mechanism (patience of 5), a batch size of 16 with gradient

accumulation of 4 steps, an adaptive learning rate using the AdaFactor optimizer, weight decay of 0.01, half-precision training (except for the mDeBERTa model, where the half-precision training is faulty), using the Macro avg. F1-score as a metric for the best model selection. The tokenizers used truncation of texts to maximum length of 512 tokens. We have done manual hyper-parameter search prior to running the fine-tuning, finding the parameters working for all detector models.

For Random Forest classifier used for entropy-based detector, we have executed optimization of hyperparameters on the train split of the dataset using automated Randomized Grid Search with 5-fold cross-validation and 1k of iterations. The grid consisted of the following parameters:

¹⁴<https://huggingface.co/roberta-large-openai-detector>
¹⁵<https://huggingface.co/gpt2-medium>
¹⁶<https://huggingface.co/xlm-roberta-large>
¹⁷<https://huggingface.co/bert-base-multilingual-cased>
¹⁸<https://huggingface.co/microsoft/mdebta-v3-base>
¹⁹<https://huggingface.co/google/electra-large-discriminator>
²⁰<https://huggingface.co/ai-forever/mGPT>
²¹https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/main_classes/trainer
²²<https://github.com/huggingface/transformers>

Detector	ar	ca	cs	de	en	es	nl	pt	ru	uk	zh
Entropy + RandomForest	0.4860	0.4721	0.4732	0.4729	0.4703	0.4697	0.4692	0.4702	0.5202	0.5040	0.4663
Entropy	0.4704	0.4705	0.4705	0.4712	0.4706	0.4720	0.4706	0.4716	0.4702	0.4704	0.4704
Rank	0.4704	0.4705	0.4705	0.4712	0.4706	0.4720	0.4706	0.4716	0.4702	0.4704	0.4704
DetectGPT	0.4704	0.4705	0.4705	0.4712	0.4706	0.4720	0.4706	0.4716	0.4702	0.4704	0.4704
Log-Rank	0.4702	0.4705	0.4705	0.4712	0.4706	0.4720	0.4706	0.4716	0.4698	0.4703	0.4644
Log-likelihood	0.4702	0.4705	0.4705	0.4712	0.4706	0.4720	0.4706	0.4716	0.4699	0.4703	0.4662
GLTR Test-2 (Rank)	0.4239	0.4702	0.4700	0.4701	0.4706	0.4720	0.4703	0.4711	0.4697	0.4697	0.4653
ZeroGPT	0.3055	0.4807	0.4509	0.4019	0.5979	0.4750	0.4625	0.4510	0.4194	0.4267	0.1398
GPTZero	0.1128	0.1057	0.1040	0.0999	0.5626	0.0973	0.1044	0.1010	0.1042	0.1014	0.1189

Table 10: Cross-lingual performance of zero-shot detection models.

- $n_estimators = [10, 50, 100, 150, 300]$ – a number of trees in the random forest,
- $criterion = ['gini', 'entropy']$ – a function to measure the quality of a split,
- $max_features = ['sqrt', 'log2', None]$ – a number of features in consideration at every split,
- $max_depth = [None, 10, 100]$ – a maximum number of levels allowed in each decision tree,
- $min_samples_split = [2, 4, 6]$ – a minimum sample number to split a node,
- $min_samples_leaf = [1, 3]$ – a minimum sample number that can be stored in a leaf node,
- $bootstrap = [True, False]$ – a method used to sample data points.

E Results Data

In Table 10, performance results (Macro average F1-score) of all statistical and black-box detectors per each test language are provided. The highest value for each test language is boldfaced.

In Tables 11–15, performance results (Macro average F1-score) of all fine-tuned detector models per each test language are provided. The highest value in a row is boldfaced. It denotes, on which test language a particular fine-tuned detector version performs the best. At the bottom of the tables, mean values of all detectors per test language are provided, along with separated mean results of multilingual and monolingual detectors’ base models.

In Tables 16–18, performance results (Macro average F1-score) of all fine-tuned detector models across individual text-generation LLM data are provided. Also in this case, the highest value in a row is boldfaced.

Table 19 shows how the text-generation LLMs correlate based on the detectors performances, separated per each train language. In Table 20, mean performance results with standard-deviation values are provided for each LLM, aggregated per each train language.

Train & Test LLM	Detector Base Model	Test Language										
		ar	ca	cs	de	en	es	nl	pt	ru	uk	zh
alpaca-lora-30b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.5375	0.8271	0.8546	0.8917	0.9567	0.7517	0.8563	0.8055	0.8374	0.8091	0.5537
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5270	0.4929	0.4819	0.3956	0.9783	0.5856	0.5448	0.5196	0.5153	0.4215	0.4642
	gpt2-medium	0.7438	0.4252	0.4513	0.3928	0.9657	0.4063	0.4233	0.3719	0.5547	0.5326	0.3742
	mGPT	0.4024	0.8089	0.6132	0.8763	0.9639	0.7390	0.8791	0.8333	0.8162	0.8210	0.4626
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.2080	0.8592	0.7691	0.9003	0.9439	0.7744	0.8977	0.8570	0.7988	0.7563	0.3099
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3484	0.6258	0.5430	0.5133	0.9238	0.4809	0.7787	0.4348	0.4029	0.4838	0.4487
xlm-roberta-large	0.4474	0.8488	0.8713	0.9324	0.9801	0.6319	0.7706	0.7130	0.8733	0.8319	0.4474	
gpt-3.5-turbo	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.9215	0.8904	0.9150	0.9020	0.9783	0.8545	0.9348	0.9124	0.9183	0.8962	0.8933
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3985	0.8409	0.3333	0.3576	0.9765	0.8243	0.7355	0.7810	0.3849	0.3526	0.3399
	gpt2-medium	0.3673	0.3407	0.3443	0.3369	0.9838	0.3264	0.3432	0.3378	0.3689	0.3710	0.3428
	mGPT	0.7009	0.9266	0.3370	0.9071	0.9892	0.8506	0.9432	0.9147	0.9013	0.9080	0.5610
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7876	0.5599	0.7803	0.8052	0.7178	0.6023	0.7790	0.6782	0.6484	0.7649	0.6733
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4174	0.6710	0.5623	0.5476	0.9166	0.5356	0.8203	0.4381	0.5442	0.6236	0.4727
xlm-roberta-large	0.7218	0.9733	0.7211	0.9392	0.9838	0.7861	0.9229	0.9281	0.8839	0.6290	0.5155	
gpt-4	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8419	0.9265	0.7592	0.8163	0.9765	0.8261	0.9265	0.8704	0.7929	0.7104	0.8360
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4448	0.5611	0.3333	0.3303	0.9928	0.7723	0.4206	0.6814	0.4044	0.3697	0.3333
	gpt2-medium	0.3853	0.3658	0.3516	0.3593	0.9928	0.3659	0.3887	0.3486	0.3969	0.3732	0.3318
	mGPT	0.6945	0.7888	0.3866	0.8365	0.9910	0.7954	0.8334	0.8658	0.8008	0.7849	0.4734
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7199	0.9733	0.8626	0.8944	0.8255	0.9435	0.9331	0.9319	0.8395	0.7668	0.5706
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5765	0.5661	0.4808	0.5395	0.9765	0.4974	0.7401	0.4077	0.6384	0.5689	0.4995
xlm-roberta-large	0.5659	0.9348	0.4987	0.8927	0.9892	0.8592	0.9499	0.9267	0.7676	0.4567	0.3587	
llama-65b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.5896	0.6070	0.6955	0.6895	0.9017	0.7998	0.5771	0.6752	0.7032	0.7020	0.5194
	electra-large-discriminator	0.6770	0.3311	0.3299	0.3386	0.9220	0.3613	0.3322	0.3538	0.4911	0.5700	0.3281
	gpt2-medium	0.3735	0.4296	0.5929	0.5370	0.8854	0.5623	0.5372	0.3950	0.4543	0.4893	0.4342
	mGPT	0.3848	0.3508	0.6898	0.7115	0.9037	0.5248	0.4102	0.4835	0.4669	0.4779	0.5233
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.5115	0.4060	0.8307	0.7162	0.9003	0.6074	0.4591	0.5413	0.7103	0.6693	0.4384
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3303	0.3528	0.3446	0.3341	0.8890	0.3460	0.3612	0.3371	0.3311	0.3449	0.3332
xlm-roberta-large	0.4779	0.4892	0.8507	0.7983	0.9165	0.7241	0.4368	0.6082	0.6899	0.6290	0.4892	
opt-66b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.4557	0.4586	0.6107	0.5890	0.8592	0.5394	0.4268	0.5635	0.5876	0.5594	0.5041
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5167	0.5157	0.6473	0.5853	0.8899	0.6591	0.5600	0.6993	0.4347	0.5061	0.3273
	gpt2-medium	0.5226	0.4138	0.3720	0.3827	0.8427	0.4202	0.3647	0.4089	0.5713	0.6213	0.4473
	mGPT	0.2959	0.5049	0.3954	0.6351	0.8931	0.5064	0.4942	0.6017	0.4416	0.4645	0.4161
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.3903	0.5181	0.6278	0.6568	0.8538	0.6053	0.4927	0.6431	0.5799	0.6016	0.5617
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3315	0.5268	0.4635	0.4038	0.8711	0.3792	0.5761	0.3714	0.3293	0.3733	0.3591
xlm-roberta-large	0.4910	0.4613	0.5495	0.6735	0.8827	0.5613	0.4187	0.5897	0.6706	0.6961	0.5358	
opt-impl-max-1.3b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.4592	0.5171	0.5792	0.5916	0.9061	0.5143	0.5136	0.4721	0.5494	0.5333	0.4390
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3264	0.5542	0.5036	0.6618	0.9819	0.8709	0.7625	0.8334	0.3309	0.3390	0.3299
	gpt2-medium	0.3869	0.7116	0.5300	0.5259	0.9368	0.5789	0.5600	0.5453	0.4733	0.5295	0.4720
	mGPT	0.3380	0.5134	0.6410	0.7450	0.9585	0.5284	0.6955	0.5212	0.4829	0.4925	0.5788
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7932	0.9731	1.0000	0.9609	0.9257	0.9023	0.9615	0.9025	0.9471	0.9570	0.7016
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3427	0.8511	0.7842	0.6490	0.9729	0.6895	0.9211	0.6590	0.3614	0.4318	0.4777
xlm-roberta-large	0.5810	0.8567	0.8657	0.8416	0.9439	0.7268	0.7684	0.6991	0.7483	0.7587	0.6237	
text-davinci-003	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7647	0.9014	0.8537	0.8554	0.9693	0.7750	0.9032	0.8408	0.7161	0.6657	0.8409
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4628	0.5751	0.4275	0.4024	0.9783	0.7471	0.5568	0.6000	0.5075	0.4826	0.4880
	gpt2-medium	0.3322	0.3333	0.3333	0.3303	0.9856	0.3264	0.3367	0.3268	0.3267	0.3361	0.3326
	mGPT	0.5393	0.9199	0.3623	0.8936	0.9783	0.7678	0.9027	0.8389	0.7713	0.6932	0.5246
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.5432	0.6398	0.8239	0.8563	0.9513	0.5774	0.7596	0.6335	0.6969	0.6015	0.7779
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4087	0.5610	0.5307	0.5112	0.9293	0.4369	0.7561	0.3902	0.4746	0.6221	0.4820
xlm-roberta-large	0.5035	0.9213	0.6965	0.8913	0.9856	0.7715	0.8973	0.8232	0.5769	0.4739	0.4377	
vicuna-13b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7913	0.8856	0.8012	0.8446	0.9747	0.7859	0.9365	0.8520	0.8309	0.8137	0.6667
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3912	0.3848	0.6025	0.5077	0.9838	0.6577	0.4839	0.5162	0.3420	0.3296	0.3551
	gpt2-medium	0.6275	0.3658	0.4420	0.4286	0.9783	0.3931	0.3921	0.3814	0.4329	0.4687	0.3502
	mGPT	0.4086	0.7888	0.5043	0.8511	0.9765	0.6633	0.8876	0.8071	0.6347	0.7088	0.5941
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.1784	0.5000	0.5018	0.6295	0.7775	0.4754	0.6191	0.5078	0.4121	0.4635	0.5888
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4179	0.6409	0.5661	0.5341	0.9348	0.5070	0.8146	0.4350	0.5180	0.5303	0.4740
xlm-roberta-large	0.3864	0.9417	0.4894	0.9086	0.9801	0.6866	0.8400	0.7163	0.7787	0.4897	0.4370	
All Detectors Mean		0.5016	0.6412	0.5909	0.6578	0.9361	0.6284	0.6703	0.6273	0.5976	0.5832	0.4902
Multilingual Base Models Mean		0.5448	0.7335	0.6793	0.8104	0.9292	0.7018	0.7508	0.7362	0.7148	0.6746	0.5580
Monolingual Base Models Mean		0.4440	0.5182	0.4730	0.4544	0.9454	0.5304	0.5629	0.4822	0.4412	0.4613	0.3999

Table 11: Cross-lingual performance of all detection models fine-tuned on the English language (evaluated per LLM).

Train & Test LLM	Detector Base Model	Test Language										
		ar	ca	cs	de	en	es	nl	pt	ru	uk	zh
alpaca-lora-30b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.6019	0.8950	0.8108	0.8765	0.7517	0.9092	0.8941	0.8943	0.8600	0.8182	0.7713
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5116	0.4754	0.3370	0.3361	0.3325	0.9348	0.5286	0.8665	0.3891	0.3820	0.3986
	gpt2-medium	0.6937	0.8090	0.6564	0.8226	0.7332	0.8935	0.8291	0.8602	0.5735	0.5679	0.4391
	mGPT	0.6980	0.8639	0.6989	0.9001	0.6589	0.9452	0.7088	0.9403	0.8366	0.8880	0.5691
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8255	0.7338	0.9110	0.9171	0.8771	0.8256	0.8038	0.7777	0.9317	0.9096	0.7954
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3578	0.7052	0.6789	0.8414	0.2717	0.9295	0.8296	0.8671	0.3587	0.3634	0.7537
xlm-roberta-large	0.6999	0.8349	0.9008	0.9493	0.9295	0.9281	0.9532	0.9301	0.8845	0.8278	0.6164	
gpt-3.5-turbo	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8896	0.9365	0.8997	0.8900	0.9169	0.9263	0.9232	0.8858	0.8949	0.8722	0.8765
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5268	0.7374	0.3333	0.3340	0.3333	0.9743	0.4290	0.9215	0.5390	0.4383	0.3333
	gpt2-medium	0.4313	0.8889	0.3900	0.3827	0.3669	0.8970	0.4874	0.8320	0.4949	0.4526	0.3355
	mGPT	0.8941	0.9650	0.3552	0.9307	0.8397	0.9692	0.8974	0.9556	0.8942	0.9196	0.6781
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9281	0.8817	0.9666	0.9577	0.9368	0.9570	0.9109	0.9089	0.8890	0.9128	0.9416
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3307	0.8610	0.8449	0.8700	0.2073	0.9153	0.8743	0.8392	0.3333	0.3311	0.7601
xlm-roberta-large	0.7671	0.9550	0.8609	0.8539	0.9801	0.9743	0.9616	0.9676	0.9093	0.7368	0.8504	
gpt-4	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8764	0.8852	0.9300	0.8808	0.7306	0.9277	0.9075	0.8679	0.8916	0.8792	0.8799
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3860	0.8103	0.3333	0.3303	0.3373	0.9571	0.5424	0.9506	0.3798	0.3670	0.3407
	gpt2-medium	0.4260	0.7906	0.4326	0.4318	0.3362	0.9143	0.4571	0.7844	0.4378	0.4042	0.3399
	mGPT	0.8491	0.8705	0.3370	0.9187	0.9476	0.9829	0.9245	0.9830	0.9016	0.8454	0.6649
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9331	0.8897	0.9549	0.9356	0.8826	0.9195	0.9331	0.9027	0.8545	0.9096	0.9045
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3322	0.9128	0.8091	0.8765	0.3602	0.9293	0.8449	0.8768	0.3370	0.3318	0.6283
xlm-roberta-large	0.5124	0.9599	0.5688	0.8011	0.9729	0.9812	0.9616	0.9676	0.5987	0.3994	0.4001	
llama-65b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7956	0.9177	0.9645	0.7711	0.3611	0.9914	0.6665	0.9794	0.8227	0.9290	0.6396
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4887	0.9026	0.9272	0.9214	0.3325	0.9741	0.8515	0.9691	0.3620	0.4606	0.3318
	gpt2-medium	0.3680	0.9365	0.8738	0.9079	0.3990	0.9621	0.8744	0.9398	0.4793	0.5608	0.5344
	mGPT	0.5912	0.6899	0.8606	0.7540	0.3505	0.9673	0.3604	0.9501	0.5401	0.8348	0.3731
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9135	0.9262	0.9882	0.9608	0.6260	0.9862	0.6591	0.9777	0.9765	0.9848	0.3539
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3296	0.8944	0.7558	0.7449	0.3357	0.9517	0.8188	0.8808	0.3392	0.3617	0.3296
xlm-roberta-large	0.8461	0.8307	0.9831	0.9557	0.6680	0.9879	0.4583	0.9725	0.9412	0.9680	0.6842	
opt-66b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7378	0.7608	0.6443	0.5872	0.4705	0.7658	0.7038	0.7662	0.6748	0.7543	0.8225
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4594	0.7202	0.6132	0.6954	0.3333	0.7692	0.6844	0.7265	0.4311	0.5203	0.3311
	gpt2-medium	0.4455	0.7310	0.4703	0.5913	0.4524	0.7703	0.5466	0.5972	0.5993	0.6464	0.4690
	mGPT	0.3906	0.7297	0.4550	0.6957	0.3722	0.7992	0.3866	0.9549	0.5713	0.6426	0.4554
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9139	0.8500	0.9883	0.9493	0.6240	0.8762	0.8538	0.7872	0.9696	0.9627	0.6997
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4668	0.6129	0.8550	0.6502	0.3355	0.8141	0.8564	0.7337	0.5548	0.5646	0.5596
xlm-roberta-large	0.6058	0.7452	0.8765	0.8104	0.4443	0.8123	0.4702	0.6335	0.8106	0.8408	0.5381	
opt-impl-max-1.3b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.9537	0.9697	0.9632	0.8676	0.6840	0.9482	0.9699	0.8820	0.9027	0.9707	0.9528
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3527	0.9681	0.8392	0.8930	0.3333	0.9515	0.8798	0.9189	0.3280	0.3305	0.3307
	gpt2-medium	0.6084	0.9049	0.7598	0.5085	0.4730	0.9100	0.6565	0.6696	0.6559	0.7088	0.3941
	mGPT	0.9434	0.9613	0.9210	0.9932	0.4045	0.9879	0.8410	0.9810	0.8970	0.9845	0.5838
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9931	0.9866	0.9933	0.8710	0.5865	0.9827	0.9329	0.9828	0.9949	0.9931	0.8744
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4128	0.9646	0.9498	0.7265	0.2160	0.9602	0.9381	0.9103	0.5456	0.6839	0.5212
xlm-roberta-large	0.9794	0.9916	0.8583	0.9881	0.6192	0.9810	0.9799	0.9793	0.7578	0.7060	0.8187	
text-davinci-003	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7319	0.9047	0.8833	0.8602	0.7605	0.9312	0.8892	0.8631	0.8027	0.7405	0.8400
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4855	0.5814	0.3333	0.3296	0.3373	0.9605	0.4529	0.8925	0.5528	0.5678	0.3370
	gpt2-medium	0.6145	0.9250	0.6295	0.7554	0.5875	0.9047	0.7750	0.8313	0.7541	0.6885	0.3355
	mGPT	0.7188	0.8020	0.3832	0.9274	0.9039	0.9657	0.9382	0.9165	0.8578	0.7165	0.7663
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.6436	0.7615	0.9248	0.9239	0.9404	0.8059	0.9065	0.8484	0.8597	0.7446	0.9166
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3329	0.5973	0.7689	0.8681	0.2113	0.9415	0.7787	0.9003	0.3337	0.3388	0.7381
xlm-roberta-large	0.7993	0.9264	0.9482	0.9510	0.9422	0.9777	0.9733	0.9352	0.8944	0.7921	0.8768	
vicuna-13b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8628	0.9149	0.7705	0.8341	0.7503	0.9281	0.8996	0.8823	0.8226	0.7869	0.8514
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4812	0.5839	0.3798	0.3827	0.3333	0.9743	0.4827	0.8677	0.5833	0.5508	0.4081
	gpt2-medium	0.7679	0.9232	0.5873	0.6943	0.7214	0.9159	0.7333	0.8299	0.5051	0.5253	0.4208
	mGPT	0.7234	0.8716	0.5427	0.9206	0.6739	0.9674	0.6880	0.9164	0.7205	0.7893	0.6191
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.6784	0.8994	0.8387	0.9052	0.9169	0.9520	0.8753	0.8956	0.8595	0.8562	0.8291
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5358	0.8853	0.6725	0.8681	0.3147	0.9432	0.8460	0.9058	0.4371	0.3755	0.5963
xlm-roberta-large	0.8447	0.8789	0.6681	0.8614	0.9061	0.9434	0.8267	0.8959	0.7773	0.6400	0.6473	
All Detectors Mean		0.6480	0.8413	0.7300	0.7850	0.5790	0.9259	0.7689	0.8749	0.6804	0.6800	0.6082
Multilingual Base Models Mean		0.7857	0.8747	0.8016	0.8812	0.7322	0.9314	0.8143	0.8944	0.8375	0.8299	0.7216
Monolingual Base Models Mean		0.4644	0.7967	0.6346	0.6568	0.3748	0.9187	0.7082	0.8488	0.4710	0.4801	0.4569

Table 12: Cross-lingual performance of all detection models fine-tuned on the Spanish language (evaluated per LLM).

Train & Test LLM	Detector Base Model	Test Language										
		ar	ca	cs	de	en	es	nl	pt	ru	uk	zh
alpaca-lora-30b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.6026	0.6327	0.8067	0.7409	0.4634	0.6572	0.6705	0.6567	0.9099	0.8829	0.6696
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4945	0.3680	0.3443	0.3516	0.3829	0.5214	0.4081	0.3884	0.5506	0.5100	0.4514
	gpt2-medium	0.7291	0.4784	0.4665	0.4094	0.6639	0.6505	0.4265	0.5331	0.8599	0.8249	0.3950
	mGPT	0.5635	0.4123	0.6725	0.8716	0.5272	0.7714	0.5325	0.7920	0.9350	0.9129	0.4906
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9716	0.8123	0.9850	0.9409	0.8550	0.8885	0.8868	0.8199	0.9617	0.9615	0.8237
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.7062	0.3326	0.3407	0.3363	0.2381	0.3394	0.3370	0.3421	0.8599	0.8464	0.5544
xlm-roberta-large	0.9180	0.8983	0.9700	0.9442	0.9169	0.9058	0.9431	0.8993	0.9433	0.9397	0.8522	
gpt-3.5-turbo	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.9416	0.8680	0.9045	0.8538	0.7810	0.8754	0.8783	0.8378	0.9567	0.9331	0.8666
	electra-large-discriminator	0.6636	0.3333	0.3333	0.3303	0.3457	0.3272	0.3330	0.3276	0.6336	0.5592	0.3333
	gpt2-medium	0.5384	0.3443	0.3407	0.3369	0.3423	0.3264	0.3403	0.3350	0.8716	0.8061	0.3333
	mGPT	0.7846	0.8857	0.3552	0.9070	0.8817	0.9228	0.9230	0.9043	0.9533	0.9244	0.6258
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9365	0.8387	0.9817	0.9256	0.9603	0.9296	0.9146	0.9023	0.9283	0.9482	0.8329
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3496	0.3472	0.3720	0.3476	0.1697	0.3471	0.3663	0.3421	0.8695	0.5855	0.6240
xlm-roberta-large	0.9332	0.9432	0.9883	0.9391	0.9675	0.9435	0.9466	0.9143	0.9767	0.9615	0.9048	
gpt-4	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8667	0.7067	0.7828	0.7535	0.4958	0.6805	0.7514	0.6918	0.9333	0.9214	0.8122
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5003	0.3311	0.3333	0.3303	0.3718	0.3374	0.3292	0.3326	0.6837	0.6241	0.3677
	gpt2-medium	0.5234	0.3587	0.3623	0.3514	0.3368	0.3659	0.3655	0.3458	0.7535	0.7794	0.3508
	mGPT	0.8978	0.8978	0.3587	0.9188	0.8713	0.9383	0.9246	0.9264	0.9566	0.8570	0.7078
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9349	0.5556	0.8788	0.9221	0.9259	0.7611	0.7609	0.6932	0.8305	0.8940	0.7797
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5936	0.3407	0.3480	0.3439	0.2994	0.3433	0.3628	0.3421	0.7991	0.8526	0.6649
xlm-roberta-large	0.9215	0.9600	0.9950	0.9391	0.9765	0.9349	0.9633	0.9368	0.9567	0.9447	0.9214	
llama-65b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7078	0.5300	0.8750	0.6477	0.3325	0.8211	0.5191	0.6043	0.9849	0.9764	0.4765
	electra-large-discriminator	0.7140	0.3303	0.3299	0.3348	0.3325	0.3383	0.3330	0.3356	0.6109	0.6025	0.3676
	gpt2-medium	0.6015	0.4216	0.6322	0.6629	0.4170	0.7424	0.5012	0.4982	0.9395	0.9394	0.5690
	mGPT	0.5347	0.3326	0.6154	0.6470	0.3325	0.4964	0.3404	0.4847	0.9782	0.9359	0.4056
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7629	0.4277	0.9848	0.8540	0.3824	0.7305	0.4145	0.5383	0.9883	0.9815	0.5622
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6454	0.3311	0.3269	0.3341	0.3388	0.3375	0.3307	0.3356	0.9631	0.9309	0.3969
xlm-roberta-large	0.8858	0.5705	0.9865	0.9160	0.3705	0.5024	0.3674	0.5826	0.9933	0.9882	0.6314	
opt-66b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7593	0.6061	0.7673	0.6078	0.4720	0.6423	0.6428	0.6734	0.9340	0.9254	0.6408
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5543	0.3326	0.3333	0.3356	0.3325	0.3394	0.3337	0.3375	0.7304	0.6932	0.3425
	gpt2-medium	0.6817	0.3755	0.3814	0.3576	0.4726	0.3972	0.3388	0.3598	0.9085	0.8797	0.4361
	mGPT	0.9714	0.5123	0.5776	0.3999	0.3473	0.4262	0.6050	0.4165	0.9662	0.9814	0.7649
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9393	0.7428	0.9833	0.4860	0.3413	0.3394	0.6255	0.3610	0.9848	0.9932	0.7645
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4195	0.3266	0.3326	0.3348	0.3046	0.3386	0.3322	0.3375	0.9003	0.8830	0.3759
xlm-roberta-large	0.9546	0.8552	0.9917	0.5544	0.3453	0.5474	0.7734	0.6168	0.9848	0.9864	0.8530	
opt-impl-max-1.3b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.9588	0.5420	0.8707	0.5073	0.3333	0.4417	0.5379	0.4153	0.9795	0.9828	0.8243
	electra-large-discriminator	0.6770	0.3709	0.5542	0.4481	0.3669	0.5480	0.4653	0.5424	0.8379	0.8536	0.7043
	gpt2-medium	0.8338	0.5143	0.4434	0.3979	0.3991	0.4127	0.4003	0.3891	0.9368	0.9188	0.5273
	mGPT	0.9640	0.6583	0.3597	0.5613	0.3750	0.3873	0.8374	0.4378	0.9949	0.9810	0.7678
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8902	0.5114	0.9379	0.5767	0.3333	0.3926	0.6230	0.3984	0.9224	0.9707	0.8335
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.7226	0.3149	0.3979	0.3242	0.1294	0.3216	0.3521	0.3245	0.9333	0.9293	0.5404
xlm-roberta-large	0.9931	0.7275	0.9900	0.7551	0.3373	0.3944	0.8638	0.4432	0.9966	0.9948	0.9338	
text-davinci-003	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7480	0.6998	0.6476	0.8087	0.7249	0.8167	0.7157	0.7645	0.9146	0.9079	0.7911
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4395	0.3348	0.3326	0.3332	0.5357	0.3413	0.3306	0.3318	0.5136	0.4716	0.3935
	gpt2-medium	0.7234	0.3333	0.3333	0.3296	0.3244	0.3264	0.3367	0.3245	0.8528	0.8408	0.3333
	mGPT	0.8798	0.6376	0.3552	0.8629	0.6831	0.8696	0.7987	0.7996	0.9315	0.8193	0.6410
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8800	0.4399	0.6877	0.5837	0.3453	0.5184	0.4845	0.5132	0.9381	0.9598	0.7358
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6924	0.3623	0.4165	0.3514	0.1657	0.3471	0.4236	0.3421	0.8814	0.8155	0.6138
xlm-roberta-large	0.8664	0.4440	0.7422	0.7117	0.3778	0.5679	0.5897	0.5700	0.9382	0.9497	0.7750	
vicuna-13b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.5450	0.3623	0.5724	0.4549	0.3333	0.4751	0.3548	0.3721	0.9264	0.8401	0.3472
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5084	0.3355	0.3376	0.3318	0.3333	0.3386	0.3306	0.3421	0.5535	0.5256	0.5498
	gpt2-medium	0.5858	0.3787	0.4784	0.4744	0.5022	0.3811	0.3954	0.4326	0.8712	0.6147	0.4456
	mGPT	0.6846	0.3407	0.8659	0.8576	0.3722	0.6188	0.3663	0.5499	0.9548	0.8978	0.5443
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9883	0.7980	0.9381	0.9033	0.8136	0.9023	0.8760	0.8464	0.9565	0.9582	0.8594
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5037	0.3326	0.3318	0.3356	0.3138	0.3394	0.3330	0.3382	0.8845	0.5946	0.6119
xlm-roberta-large	0.9716	0.7526	0.9280	0.9391	0.8572	0.9298	0.6979	0.8416	0.9615	0.9278	0.8998	
All Detectors Mean		0.7421	0.5274	0.6171	0.5914	0.4795	0.5614	0.5524	0.5369	0.8870	0.8557	0.6183
Multilingual Base Models Mean		0.8487	0.6532	0.7924	0.7591	0.5760	0.6884	0.6915	0.6626	0.9522	0.9387	0.7294
Monolingual Base Models Mean		0.6001	0.3596	0.3835	0.3677	0.3508	0.3920	0.3669	0.3692	0.8000	0.7451	0.4701

Table 13: Cross-lingual performance of all detection models fine-tuned on the Russian language (evaluated per LLM).

Train & Test LLM	Detector Base Model	Test Language										
		ar	ca	cs	de	en	es	nl	pt	ru	uk	zh
alpaca-lora-30b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.5096	0.9133	0.8879	0.9138	0.9657	0.9401	0.9161	0.9113	0.9200	0.8928	0.7472
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3367	0.7431	0.4389	0.5051	0.9856	0.9502	0.7716	0.8824	0.3407	0.3326	0.3999
	gpt2-medium	0.8118	0.7896	0.6623	0.7747	0.9819	0.8919	0.8064	0.8307	0.8463	0.8251	0.4282
	mGPT	0.6955	0.8833	0.6480	0.9290	0.9585	0.9315	0.8215	0.9334	0.9383	0.9129	0.5555
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8438	0.8062	0.8906	0.8727	0.9075	0.8643	0.8044	0.8364	0.9283	0.9331	0.7118
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.8040	0.7010	0.8484	0.8629	0.9348	0.9363	0.8641	0.8969	0.8817	0.8487	0.7252
xlm-roberta-large	0.7742	0.9283	0.9600	0.9578	0.9856	0.9589	0.9481	0.9522	0.9366	0.9246	0.8200	
gpt-3.5-turbo	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8483	0.9750	0.9633	0.9391	0.9819	0.9777	0.9816	0.9506	0.9550	0.9313	0.9148
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3501	0.7954	0.3333	0.3340	0.9819	0.9657	0.4354	0.8583	0.3326	0.3326	0.3901
	gpt2-medium	0.6911	0.9180	0.5441	0.6283	0.9874	0.9452	0.7647	0.8586	0.8480	0.6995	0.3333
	mGPT	0.8856	0.9198	0.3552	0.8964	0.9801	0.9469	0.9566	0.9370	0.9383	0.8939	0.5693
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9466	0.8710	0.9767	0.9578	0.9747	0.9280	0.8977	0.9039	0.9232	0.9398	0.8526
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5451	0.6366	0.6189	0.7365	0.9765	0.9726	0.5633	0.9710	0.8933	0.5315	0.4295
xlm-roberta-large	0.9280	0.9850	0.9883	0.9425	0.9910	0.9846	0.9800	0.9727	0.9850	0.9464	0.9382	
gpt-4	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.9416	0.9566	0.9533	0.9255	0.9928	0.9485	0.9683	0.9453	0.9400	0.9365	0.9048
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3330	0.9297	0.3333	0.3593	0.9946	0.9726	0.8213	0.9472	0.3333	0.3326	0.3333
	gpt2-medium	0.7644	0.8923	0.6236	0.6851	0.9982	0.9279	0.7007	0.8714	0.8516	0.8235	0.3392
	mGPT	0.8911	0.9450	0.3407	0.9014	0.9928	0.9640	0.9246	0.9487	0.9467	0.9212	0.7236
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9382	0.9315	0.9883	0.9797	0.9457	0.9502	0.9582	0.9195	0.9383	0.9498	0.8854
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.7820	0.8696	0.8308	0.8932	0.9838	0.9657	0.7753	0.9590	0.8548	0.7828	0.5290
xlm-roberta-large	0.9599	0.9733	0.9850	0.9696	0.9946	0.9691	0.9816	0.9829	0.9733	0.9833	0.9365	
llama-65b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7821	0.8645	0.9288	0.7867	0.9076	0.9879	0.7835	0.9449	0.9782	0.9781	0.6580
	electra-large-discriminator	0.7392	0.9281	0.9320	0.9455	0.8964	0.9862	0.8995	0.9570	0.9189	0.9443	0.6784
	gpt2-medium	0.6580	0.9632	0.9491	0.9490	0.9016	0.9845	0.9279	0.9605	0.9765	0.9697	0.6849
	mGPT	0.8919	0.8853	0.9509	0.9058	0.9293	0.9862	0.7192	0.9691	0.9799	0.9731	0.5337
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8006	0.8887	0.9831	0.8061	0.9004	0.9828	0.6450	0.9535	0.9899	0.9663	0.5974
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6731	0.9766	0.9763	0.8597	0.9239	0.9862	0.9598	0.9690	0.9714	0.9781	0.4521
xlm-roberta-large	0.7446	0.8013	0.9373	0.8827	0.8984	0.9914	0.4673	0.9448	0.9899	0.9798	0.5992	
opt-66b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7967	0.7219	0.7674	0.7282	0.8716	0.8097	0.6880	0.8256	0.9168	0.9000	0.7730
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4285	0.7333	0.6311	0.7610	0.8950	0.7945	0.7222	0.8359	0.3401	0.3394	0.3731
	gpt2-medium	0.6023	0.8078	0.6790	0.7160	0.8877	0.7941	0.6774	0.7390	0.9070	0.8897	0.5969
	mGPT	0.9069	0.8440	0.8010	0.8186	0.9043	0.8626	0.7591	0.8012	0.9747	0.9729	0.6929
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8913	0.9396	1.0000	0.8978	0.8479	0.8847	0.8763	0.8646	0.9882	0.9831	0.8073
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6401	0.6683	0.8647	0.7966	0.9097	0.8645	0.8275	0.8683	0.8985	0.8812	0.6668
xlm-roberta-large	0.9410	0.9514	0.9967	0.8348	0.8879	0.8695	0.8959	0.9212	0.9746	0.9966	0.7806	
opt-impl-max-1.3b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.9503	0.9327	0.9598	0.8388	0.9206	0.9219	0.9006	0.9224	0.9863	0.9845	0.9494
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3386	0.9243	0.8798	0.8805	0.9801	0.9672	0.9381	0.9378	0.3425	0.3429	0.4383
	gpt2-medium	0.6676	0.9815	0.9295	0.8375	0.9548	0.9585	0.9159	0.8588	0.9281	0.9255	0.6572
	mGPT	0.9760	0.9597	0.9243	0.9524	0.9567	0.9793	0.9565	0.9707	0.9983	0.9966	0.7681
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.9760	0.9882	1.0000	0.9575	0.9205	0.9672	0.9732	0.9810	1.0000	0.9966	0.7999
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6580	0.9511	0.9783	0.9405	0.9675	0.9810	0.9799	0.9326	0.9215	0.9191	0.6601
xlm-roberta-large	0.9863	0.9966	1.0000	0.9932	0.9054	0.9689	0.9916	0.9707	1.0000	0.9983	0.8078	
text-davinci-003	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8246	0.9583	0.9349	0.9527	0.9639	0.9640	0.9616	0.9351	0.9098	0.8775	0.9183
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3330	0.7572	0.3333	0.3377	0.9838	0.9623	0.5772	0.8433	0.3337	0.3330	0.3781
	gpt2-medium	0.7628	0.9299	0.6175	0.7370	0.9819	0.9365	0.7891	0.8164	0.8564	0.8406	0.4081
	mGPT	0.8462	0.6847	0.3333	0.9730	0.9801	0.9743	0.9599	0.9438	0.9499	0.8396	0.8442
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7598	0.8536	0.9516	0.9118	0.8964	0.8446	0.8755	0.8891	0.9349	0.9244	0.9331
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6837	0.7831	0.8645	0.8792	0.8488	0.9257	0.8654	0.8806	0.8556	0.8590	0.6139
xlm-roberta-large	0.6706	0.7938	0.8870	0.9357	0.9693	0.9298	0.9649	0.9062	0.9041	0.8336	0.6714	
vicuna-13b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8294	0.9533	0.8963	0.8902	0.9603	0.9486	0.9599	0.9420	0.9398	0.8928	0.7173
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3548	0.8538	0.4133	0.4349	0.9874	0.9536	0.6708	0.9148	0.3703	0.3400	0.4983
	gpt2-medium	0.7526	0.9010	0.6593	0.6846	0.9838	0.9331	0.7428	0.8293	0.8517	0.6033	0.4810
	mGPT	0.8467	0.8620	0.5100	0.9031	0.9801	0.9398	0.8907	0.9352	0.9413	0.8451	0.6522
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8543	0.8078	0.8991	0.9204	0.8907	0.8410	0.8596	0.8721	0.9363	0.9364	0.7012
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.7635	0.9214	0.8653	0.9070	0.9729	0.9570	0.8976	0.9281	0.8671	0.7857	0.7200
xlm-roberta-large	0.8809	0.9517	0.9348	0.9594	0.9819	0.9709	0.9179	0.9213	0.9749	0.9565	0.7442	
All Detectors Mean		0.7463	0.8765	0.7918	0.8300	0.9472	0.9375	0.8407	0.9099	0.8592	0.8296	0.6558
Multilingual Base Models Mean		0.8537	0.8977	0.8604	0.9073	0.9420	0.9372	0.8808	0.9253	0.9560	0.9374	0.7659
Monolingual Base Models Mean		0.6031	0.8482	0.7003	0.7269	0.9542	0.9380	0.7872	0.8895	0.7301	0.6859	0.5090

Table 14: Cross-lingual performance of all detection models fine-tuned on all three train languages (evaluated per LLM).

Train & Test LLM	Detector Base Model	Test Language										
		ar	ca	cs	de	en	es	nl	pt	ru	uk	zh
alpaca-lora-30b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.4951	0.8743	0.8600	0.9053	0.9838	0.7617	0.9079	0.8579	0.8461	0.8144	0.5719
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3770	0.4539	0.4389	0.3827	0.9892	0.5344	0.4379	0.4684	0.3363	0.3333	0.4711
	gpt2-medium	0.3656	0.4420	0.4544	0.4038	0.9928	0.4063	0.4297	0.3814	0.3854	0.4195	0.4141
	mGPT	0.2930	0.7623	0.4958	0.8850	0.9801	0.7360	0.8594	0.8655	0.8209	0.8043	0.4268
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.1764	0.6872	0.8096	0.8529	0.9385	0.6356	0.7888	0.7340	0.7332	0.6824	0.4177
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3448	0.4963	0.4613	0.4216	0.9711	0.3945	0.6572	0.3721	0.3571	0.4340	0.4346
xlm-roberta-large	0.3306	0.8378	0.8782	0.9425	0.9874	0.6985	0.9007	0.7872	0.8294	0.8524	0.5984	
gpt-3.5-turbo	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.9449	0.9178	0.9383	0.9257	0.9819	0.8718	0.9499	0.9298	0.9100	0.8946	0.9083
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4179	0.4001	0.3407	0.3524	0.9856	0.6747	0.4557	0.5561	0.4058	0.3972	0.3132
	gpt2-medium	0.3690	0.3407	0.3370	0.3450	0.9910	0.3301	0.3432	0.3313	0.3658	0.3539	0.3333
	mGPT	0.6786	0.9083	0.3333	0.9049	0.9874	0.8874	0.9633	0.9284	0.9232	0.8860	0.5494
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8148	0.7353	0.8158	0.8783	0.9258	0.7020	0.8267	0.7834	0.6769	0.7348	0.7295
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6747	0.9182	0.8488	0.8416	0.9693	0.7811	0.8637	0.7284	0.6661	0.3600	0.5888
xlm-roberta-large	0.9199	0.9800	0.9750	0.9408	0.9838	0.9192	0.9549	0.9385	0.9517	0.9464	0.7963	
gpt-4	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8350	0.9009	0.9200	0.9307	0.9964	0.7323	0.9382	0.8389	0.8766	0.8662	0.8079
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4747	0.6222	0.3363	0.4691	0.9910	0.8320	0.5694	0.7838	0.3804	0.3378	0.3370
	gpt2-medium	0.3759	0.3516	0.3370	0.3413	0.9982	0.3553	0.3540	0.3565	0.3725	0.3468	0.3407
	mGPT	0.8481	0.9299	0.3333	0.9104	0.9928	0.7951	0.9314	0.9072	0.8798	0.8067	0.6570
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8199	0.7249	0.9076	0.8679	0.6291	0.6506	0.8023	0.7064	0.7794	0.8271	0.6940
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5115	0.6923	0.5428	0.6090	0.9892	0.4870	0.7771	0.4381	0.4911	0.4030	0.6774
xlm-roberta-large	0.8780	0.9093	0.9566	0.9645	0.9946	0.8286	0.9248	0.8808	0.9066	0.9298	0.8614	
llama-65b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.6552	0.6417	0.7971	0.7019	0.9219	0.8057	0.6370	0.6880	0.7016	0.8031	0.5659
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3311	0.3363	0.3336	0.3536	0.9365	0.3537	0.3330	0.3395	0.3311	0.3326	0.3318
	gpt2-medium	0.3472	0.3979	0.5536	0.4564	0.9384	0.5798	0.3912	0.4192	0.3844	0.3912	0.4145
	mGPT	0.3369	0.3616	0.7761	0.7157	0.9147	0.5517	0.4591	0.5616	0.4846	0.5137	0.5556
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7477	0.6646	0.9272	0.7560	0.8959	0.8662	0.6821	0.7176	0.7734	0.8533	0.5902
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3311	0.3607	0.3545	0.3408	0.9457	0.3460	0.3761	0.3395	0.3355	0.3529	0.3325
xlm-roberta-large	0.4532	0.4074	0.8414	0.7198	0.9384	0.6397	0.4080	0.5535	0.6371	0.6560	0.4488	
opt-66b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.4121	0.5241	0.6850	0.6789	0.9079	0.5558	0.5274	0.6377	0.6104	0.6477	0.5323
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3969	0.6936	0.6463	0.6972	0.9314	0.6785	0.6637	0.7006	0.3390	0.3303	0.3311
	gpt2-medium	0.4448	0.4992	0.4264	0.5941	0.8898	0.5432	0.4274	0.6423	0.4870	0.5507	0.4764
	mGPT	0.1983	0.5890	0.5708	0.6564	0.9185	0.5605	0.5826	0.6449	0.4463	0.4981	0.4464
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.2612	0.4316	0.5316	0.6257	0.7720	0.4713	0.4184	0.3897	0.5503	0.4716	0.5307
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3322	0.6773	0.4695	0.4529	0.9332	0.4155	0.6678	0.4105	0.3346	0.3886	0.3376
xlm-roberta-large	0.4182	0.4089	0.6021	0.6750	0.9205	0.5871	0.4205	0.5935	0.5884	0.6220	0.5175	
opt-impl-max-1.3b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.5705	0.6372	0.7086	0.7003	0.9549	0.6327	0.6705	0.6447	0.5501	0.6380	0.5188
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3280	0.6391	0.6211	0.7352	0.9964	0.8875	0.8502	0.8454	0.3280	0.3275	0.3292
	gpt2-medium	0.3740	0.8301	0.5994	0.6433	0.9801	0.7471	0.6005	0.6545	0.3770	0.3929	0.4977
	mGPT	0.2607	0.5663	0.5731	0.6369	0.9729	0.5881	0.5901	0.4952	0.2563	0.2537	0.4156
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7309	0.8618	0.9212	0.8152	0.9729	0.7726	0.8558	0.7391	0.7542	0.8477	0.7328
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3280	0.8886	0.7955	0.6782	0.9856	0.7670	0.9075	0.6858	0.3429	0.4533	0.3737
xlm-roberta-large	0.6694	0.7393	0.7423	0.8130	0.9711	0.7553	0.6195	0.6933	0.5689	0.5977	0.6165	
text-davinci-003	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7853	0.9064	0.8815	0.8951	0.9693	0.7987	0.9115	0.8632	0.7773	0.7333	0.8883
	electra-large-discriminator	0.3985	0.3333	0.3333	0.3303	0.9910	0.3309	0.3330	0.3284	0.3741	0.4089	0.3333
	gpt2-medium	0.3330	0.3333	0.3333	0.3303	0.9892	0.3264	0.3330	0.3276	0.3283	0.3334	0.3326
	mGPT	0.6136	0.8932	0.3333	0.8701	0.9892	0.8484	0.9382	0.9079	0.6940	0.5687	0.5904
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.5791	0.7680	0.8940	0.8895	0.9074	0.6401	0.8748	0.7725	0.7341	0.6130	0.7199
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5757	0.7601	0.8132	0.8724	0.9946	0.7930	0.7339	0.7721	0.6125	0.3726	0.6949
xlm-roberta-large	0.3899	0.9042	0.5268	0.9016	0.9856	0.8327	0.9482	0.8872	0.5981	0.3932	0.3987	
vicuna-13b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7679	0.8821	0.8366	0.8410	0.9874	0.7861	0.9382	0.8218	0.8335	0.8378	0.6379
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4056	0.5004	0.5494	0.5233	0.9838	0.7749	0.6136	0.6435	0.4744	0.4347	0.5352
	gpt2-medium	0.5084	0.3728	0.4513	0.4422	0.9856	0.5856	0.3776	0.4527	0.4134	0.4440	0.3841
	mGPT	0.3881	0.9079	0.4889	0.8254	0.9910	0.6963	0.9161	0.8043	0.6361	0.7215	0.6778
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.2578	0.7861	0.6983	0.8225	0.7928	0.6142	0.8809	0.7064	0.6031	0.6765	0.5488
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.3330	0.4906	0.4113	0.4794	0.9511	0.4425	0.6971	0.3821	0.3326	0.3341	0.3488
xlm-roberta-large	0.4062	0.9009	0.7648	0.9324	0.9892	0.6761	0.8613	0.7444	0.7618	0.7866	0.7595	
All Detectors Mean		0.4931	0.6568	0.6270	0.6871	0.9529	0.6476	0.6800	0.6497	0.5759	0.5716	0.5299
Multilingual Base Models Mean		0.5605	0.7484	0.7289	0.8244	0.9392	0.7156	0.7778	0.7508	0.7092	0.7118	0.6160
Monolingual Base Models Mean		0.4033	0.5346	0.4912	0.5040	0.9712	0.5570	0.5497	0.5150	0.3981	0.3847	0.4152

Table 15: Cross-lingual performance of all detection models fine-tuned on the English language with 3-times more train samples (evaluated per LLM).

Train LLM	Detector Base Model	Test LLM							
		text-davinci-003	gpt-3.5-turbo	gpt-4	alpaca-lora-30b	vicuna-13b	llama-65b	opt-66b	opt-impl-max-1.3b
alpaca-lora-30b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8102	0.8237	0.7964	0.7889	0.7622	0.4336	0.4315	0.4863
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5356	0.5243	0.5001	0.5698	0.5460	0.4060	0.4595	0.5168
	gpt2-medium	0.5267	0.4589	0.4438	0.5426	0.4768	0.5626	0.4401	0.4939
	mGPT	0.7656	0.8022	0.7437	0.7556	0.7396	0.4427	0.4386	0.3624
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7795	0.8118	0.8242	0.7428	0.7404	0.3676	0.3285	0.3175
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5663	0.5660	0.5646	0.5627	0.5556	0.4595	0.5272	0.5061
xlrm-roberta-large	0.7940	0.8264	0.8029	0.7643	0.7542	0.4912	0.4660	0.5107	
gpt-3.5-turbo	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8512	0.9106	0.8841	0.7797	0.8281	0.3758	0.4023	0.3959
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5937	0.6052	0.5879	0.6016	0.6087	0.4381	0.4511	0.4864
	gpt2-medium	0.4147	0.4302	0.4382	0.4215	0.4532	0.4995	0.3672	0.4162
	mGPT	0.7572	0.8286	0.7858	0.6841	0.7503	0.3726	0.3879	0.3457
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.6966	0.7136	0.7313	0.6586	0.6704	0.3248	0.2977	0.2729
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6167	0.6141	0.6105	0.6013	0.5940	0.4211	0.5461	0.4714
xlrm-roberta-large	0.7198	0.8308	0.7862	0.6829	0.7215	0.3967	0.4055	0.3881	
gpt-4	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7090	0.7954	0.8458	0.6428	0.6632	0.3744	0.3749	0.3585
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4972	0.5225	0.5362	0.4759	0.5156	0.3720	0.3757	0.3755
	gpt2-medium	0.4037	0.4334	0.4460	0.4199	0.4387	0.5207	0.3628	0.4035
	mGPT	0.7058	0.7616	0.7657	0.6387	0.6981	0.4186	0.4255	0.3558
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.6201	0.8077	0.8469	0.5331	0.6150	0.3346	0.3385	0.3357
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6070	0.6131	0.6136	0.5804	0.5889	0.3577	0.5085	0.3777
xlrm-roberta-large	0.6526	0.7151	0.7742	0.5707	0.6754	0.3815	0.3821	0.3743	
llama-65b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.2969	0.3174	0.4327	0.3828	0.4522	0.6841	0.6015	0.6403
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5096	0.4843	0.4806	0.4937	0.4921	0.5111	0.5108	0.5095
	gpt2-medium	0.4531	0.4221	0.4092	0.4193	0.4644	0.5337	0.4957	0.4954
	mGPT	0.4849	0.4824	0.5086	0.4783	0.5308	0.5608	0.5337	0.5410
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.5439	0.5356	0.5626	0.5473	0.6054	0.6348	0.6075	0.6318
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4157	0.4153	0.4157	0.4131	0.4133	0.4124	0.4099	0.4060
xlrm-roberta-large	0.4817	0.4691	0.5183	0.5133	0.5757	0.6625	0.6145	0.6553	
opt-66b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.4144	0.4443	0.5264	0.4583	0.5037	0.6291	0.5623	0.5766
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4734	0.4710	0.5217	0.5028	0.5515	0.6779	0.5974	0.6285
	gpt2-medium	0.5210	0.4556	0.4574	0.4769	0.4977	0.6650	0.5379	0.5676
	mGPT	0.5835	0.6185	0.6248	0.4870	0.6169	0.6016	0.5344	0.4388
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.4586	0.5203	0.5924	0.4266	0.6025	0.6556	0.5969	0.5744
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4785	0.4776	0.4787	0.4731	0.4726	0.4619	0.4708	0.4719
xlrm-roberta-large	0.5180	0.5048	0.5545	0.4707	0.5929	0.7085	0.6116	0.6762	
opt-impl-max-1.3b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.5108	0.5289	0.5330	0.5173	0.5442	0.5635	0.5450	0.5626
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4745	0.4613	0.4788	0.5011	0.5009	0.6021	0.5657	0.6240
	gpt2-medium	0.5220	0.4936	0.5053	0.5192	0.5431	0.6894	0.5497	0.6141
	mGPT	0.6135	0.6200	0.6061	0.6004	0.6331	0.6238	0.5904	0.6172
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.5972	0.5374	0.5093	0.6664	0.7953	0.8235	0.8139	0.9138
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6543	0.6591	0.6491	0.6438	0.6535	0.5722	0.6484	0.6772
xlrm-roberta-large	0.5576	0.5218	0.5196	0.5736	0.6675	0.7572	0.6830	0.7731	
text-davinci-003	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8289	0.8692	0.8116	0.7427	0.7640	0.3490	0.3876	0.3703
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5878	0.5924	0.5310	0.5775	0.5942	0.4013	0.4614	0.5302
	gpt2-medium	0.4172	0.4284	0.4378	0.4176	0.4411	0.4916	0.3651	0.4088
	mGPT	0.7636	0.8044	0.7709	0.6834	0.7306	0.3624	0.4103	0.3518
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7193	0.7398	0.7533	0.6600	0.6873	0.3190	0.3248	0.2649
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5722	0.5691	0.5671	0.5618	0.5534	0.4024	0.5216	0.4817
xlrm-roberta-large	0.7430	0.7991	0.7469	0.6847	0.7062	0.4158	0.4656	0.5216	
vicuna-13b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8212	0.8745	0.8672	0.7552	0.8353	0.4419	0.4167	0.4256
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5655	0.5769	0.5669	0.5823	0.5920	0.5197	0.5161	0.6136
	gpt2-medium	0.5558	0.4521	0.4421	0.5117	0.5204	0.5360	0.4994	0.5329
	mGPT	0.7242	0.7568	0.7366	0.6741	0.7312	0.4275	0.4706	0.3665
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.5538	0.5773	0.5925	0.5141	0.5328	0.4013	0.2795	0.2131
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6170	0.6150	0.6093	0.6029	0.5980	0.4421	0.5623	0.5310
xlrm-roberta-large	0.7038	0.7807	0.7476	0.6598	0.7234	0.4878	0.4896	0.5116	

Table 16: Cross-generator performance of all detection models fine-tuned on the English language (evaluated per LLM).

Train LLM	Detector Base Model	Test LLM							
		text-davinci-003	gpt-3.5-turbo	gpt-4	alpaca-lora-30b	vicuna-13b	llama-65b	opt-66b	opt-impl-max-1.3b
alpaca-lora-30b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8581	0.8905	0.8078	0.8295	0.8268	0.5157	0.4523	0.5286
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5473	0.5414	0.5105	0.5562	0.5624	0.5363	0.4681	0.4795
	gpt2-medium	0.6630	0.5975	0.4491	0.7259	0.5730	0.5714	0.4916	0.5837
	mGPT	0.7748	0.8005	0.6966	0.8025	0.7508	0.6114	0.5314	0.5592
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8632	0.8505	0.8237	0.8465	0.8484	0.4766	0.5173	0.6004
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6667	0.6847	0.6452	0.6807	0.6629	0.5254	0.4764	0.3758
xlml-roberta-large	0.8169	0.8136	0.6452	0.8599	0.7653	0.4279	0.4353	0.5307	
gpt-3.5-turbo	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8364	0.9011	0.8290	0.7524	0.7909	0.3473	0.3842	0.3736
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5457	0.5958	0.5620	0.5250	0.5732	0.4545	0.4451	0.4277
	gpt2-medium	0.5610	0.5785	0.5022	0.5185	0.5366	0.5299	0.3966	0.5121
	mGPT	0.7977	0.8596	0.8033	0.7172	0.7721	0.3934	0.4093	0.3702
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8451	0.9266	0.9040	0.7635	0.8030	0.3472	0.3405	0.3264
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6670	0.6981	0.6875	0.6202	0.6554	0.4468	0.4257	0.3329
xlml-roberta-large	0.8127	0.8939	0.8010	0.7125	0.7738	0.3816	0.3816	0.4005	
gpt-4	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8240	0.8702	0.8802	0.7418	0.7969	0.4285	0.4251	0.3798
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5456	0.5537	0.5785	0.5060	0.5510	0.4553	0.4632	0.4512
	gpt2-medium	0.4109	0.5059	0.5551	0.4236	0.4680	0.5172	0.3713	0.4303
	mGPT	0.7428	0.8420	0.8526	0.6301	0.7372	0.4196	0.3823	0.3614
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7977	0.9095	0.9113	0.6895	0.7768	0.3573	0.3471	0.3371
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6422	0.6892	0.7063	0.5845	0.6375	0.4231	0.3862	0.3187
xlml-roberta-large	0.6783	0.7627	0.7680	0.6233	0.7000	0.3695	0.3670	0.3783	
llama-65b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.3458	0.3815	0.4299	0.4424	0.5081	0.8214	0.6687	0.7356
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4849	0.4632	0.4809	0.5045	0.5231	0.7180	0.5699	0.6151
	gpt2-medium	0.4832	0.4536	0.4721	0.4963	0.5024	0.7405	0.5325	0.5924
	mGPT	0.5262	0.5447	0.5199	0.5776	0.5742	0.6943	0.5542	0.6419
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.4746	0.4224	0.4382	0.5887	0.6442	0.8678	0.7715	0.8579
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6111	0.6331	0.6282	0.5793	0.6229	0.6602	0.5422	0.4934
xlml-roberta-large	0.4259	0.4284	0.4451	0.5757	0.6168	0.8565	0.7240	0.8332	
opt-66b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.5182	0.5420	0.5370	0.5378	0.6400	0.7476	0.7074	0.7397
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4604	0.4612	0.4785	0.4740	0.5282	0.6504	0.6009	0.6205
	gpt2-medium	0.5741	0.5033	0.4575	0.5371	0.5645	0.6102	0.6019	0.6506
	mGPT	0.5684	0.5752	0.5390	0.5698	0.5986	0.5700	0.5972	0.6038
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.6073	0.4019	0.4000	0.7470	0.7419	0.8027	0.8651	0.8861
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6509	0.6478	0.6341	0.6311	0.6360	0.6075	0.6683	0.6683
xlml-roberta-large	0.5889	0.4781	0.4654	0.6340	0.6626	0.7066	0.7053	0.7086	
opt-impl-max-1.3b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.3503	0.3595	0.3455	0.4341	0.5012	0.7651	0.6947	0.9178
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5284	0.5251	0.4909	0.5445	0.5738	0.6557	0.5849	0.7075
	gpt2-medium	0.5215	0.4668	0.4399	0.4763	0.5111	0.5719	0.4972	0.6770
	mGPT	0.4806	0.4060	0.3641	0.6005	0.5902	0.7384	0.6777	0.8787
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.4692	0.3456	0.3352	0.5788	0.5674	0.5690	0.8046	0.9323
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6303	0.6232	0.5829	0.6268	0.6424	0.5714	0.6498	0.7347
xlml-roberta-large	0.3438	0.3310	0.3320	0.4737	0.4500	0.5210	0.6757	0.8856	
text-davinci-003	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8398	0.8700	0.7840	0.7585	0.8105	0.3832	0.4459	0.4992
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5908	0.5807	0.5429	0.5449	0.5745	0.4342	0.4713	0.4590
	gpt2-medium	0.7275	0.6582	0.4750	0.6549	0.6159	0.4904	0.4822	0.6132
	mGPT	0.8230	0.8604	0.7730	0.7351	0.7823	0.4025	0.4022	0.3777
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8459	0.8898	0.8881	0.7783	0.8136	0.3620	0.3554	0.3517
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6641	0.6923	0.6602	0.6147	0.6459	0.4523	0.4150	0.3379
xlml-roberta-large	0.9113	0.9345	0.8569	0.7909	0.8627	0.3898	0.4001	0.4358	
vicuna-13b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8525	0.8954	0.8444	0.7812	0.8483	0.4819	0.4452	0.4992
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5415	0.5950	0.5707	0.5428	0.6017	0.5586	0.4745	0.4876
	gpt2-medium	0.7084	0.6886	0.5819	0.6673	0.7066	0.5962	0.5040	0.6613
	mGPT	0.7824	0.7967	0.7664	0.7500	0.7815	0.6007	0.5111	0.4828
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8518	0.9009	0.8630	0.7728	0.8656	0.4793	0.4083	0.4794
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.6966	0.7304	0.6872	0.6489	0.7141	0.5363	0.4789	0.4041
xlml-roberta-large	0.7742	0.7924	0.6991	0.7086	0.8133	0.5095	0.5060	0.6679	

Table 17: Cross-generator performance of all detection models fine-tuned on the Spanish language (evaluated per LLM).

Train LLM	Detector Base Model	Test LLM							
		text-davinci-003	gpt-3.5-turbo	gpt-4	alpaca-lora-30b	vicuna-13b	llama-65b	opt-66b	opt-impl-max-1.3b
alpaca-lora-30b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7279	0.7424	0.7276	0.7127	0.7079	0.4906	0.4891	0.5071
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4746	0.4737	0.4906	0.4889	0.4873	0.6388	0.5265	0.5725
	gpt2-medium	0.4154	0.4978	0.4338	0.6095	0.4154	0.5750	0.3855	0.4667
	mGPT	0.6885	0.7089	0.6610	0.7077	0.6784	0.5698	0.5004	0.4986
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8700	0.8366	0.7959	0.9018	0.8637	0.5788	0.7436	0.8611
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5134	0.5240	0.5139	0.5359	0.4923	0.4890	0.4723	0.4254
xlml-roberta-large	0.8739	0.8502	0.7762	0.9212	0.8470	0.5112	0.5750	0.8006	
gpt-3.5-turbo	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.8358	0.8834	0.8548	0.7617	0.8171	0.3808	0.4363	0.4259
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4347	0.4889	0.4983	0.4408	0.4384	0.4084	0.3857	0.3908
	gpt2-medium	0.4234	0.4879	0.4599	0.4539	0.4328	0.4395	0.3623	0.4325
	mGPT	0.7712	0.8387	0.7840	0.7107	0.7594	0.3828	0.4280	0.3666
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8608	0.9185	0.9074	0.8127	0.8515	0.4025	0.3799	0.3644
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4998	0.5257	0.5247	0.5126	0.4993	0.4612	0.4788	0.3629
xlml-roberta-large	0.9057	0.9472	0.9320	0.8523	0.8832	0.4311	0.4196	0.4130	
gpt-4	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7354	0.7671	0.7747	0.6645	0.7139	0.4094	0.4649	0.4051
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4297	0.4782	0.4788	0.4560	0.4521	0.4829	0.4246	0.4328
	gpt2-medium	0.4549	0.4935	0.5003	0.4893	0.4583	0.4802	0.4106	0.4643
	mGPT	0.7582	0.8458	0.8566	0.6444	0.7497	0.3996	0.4090	0.3656
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.7805	0.8126	0.8134	0.7199	0.7597	0.3770	0.3834	0.3425
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4814	0.4983	0.5355	0.4818	0.4794	0.4322	0.4600	0.3530
xlml-roberta-large	0.8743	0.9378	0.9499	0.7668	0.8342	0.3855	0.3779	0.3651	
llama-65b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.4444	0.4964	0.5551	0.4455	0.5476	0.7071	0.6247	0.6517
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4662	0.4574	0.4546	0.4690	0.4708	0.5003	0.4754	0.4648
	gpt2-medium	0.3999	0.4182	0.4093	0.4423	0.4377	0.6506	0.4791	0.4855
	mGPT	0.4844	0.4835	0.4891	0.5283	0.5146	0.5925	0.5171	0.5794
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.5546	0.4236	0.4816	0.6273	0.6372	0.7263	0.7123	0.7260
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4379	0.4328	0.4487	0.4540	0.4430	0.5352	0.4778	0.4396
xlml-roberta-large	0.4767	0.4478	0.4730	0.5810	0.5973	0.7443	0.7012	0.7417	
opt-66b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.3359	0.3343	0.3592	0.3989	0.4029	0.7943	0.7091	0.7573
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4473	0.4202	0.4189	0.4424	0.4409	0.4619	0.4759	0.4674
	gpt2-medium	0.4902	0.4222	0.3950	0.4765	0.4634	0.5932	0.5526	0.5827
	mGPT	0.3959	0.3604	0.3596	0.5127	0.4866	0.6481	0.6793	0.8315
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.4262	0.3398	0.3375	0.5127	0.4807	0.4615	0.7289	0.8663
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4435	0.4209	0.4359	0.4382	0.4294	0.4511	0.4890	0.4148
xlml-roberta-large	0.3934	0.3304	0.3320	0.5074	0.4554	0.6092	0.7948	0.9364	
opt-impl-max-1.3b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.3321	0.3321	0.3327	0.3456	0.3372	0.3776	0.4305	0.7076
	electra-large-discriminator	0.5100	0.4353	0.3585	0.5607	0.4552	0.5110	0.5510	0.5909
	gpt2-medium	0.4438	0.3922	0.3737	0.4431	0.4279	0.5229	0.4935	0.5983
	mGPT	0.3341	0.3257	0.3381	0.3707	0.3652	0.4328	0.4766	0.7054
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.3482	0.3401	0.3371	0.4485	0.3843	0.3611	0.5402	0.7068
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5199	0.4835	0.4789	0.4998	0.4926	0.4773	0.5193	0.5197
xlml-roberta-large	0.3360	0.3323	0.3312	0.4210	0.3627	0.3791	0.5594	0.7996	
text-davinci-003	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.7808	0.7940	0.6553	0.7189	0.6841	0.3456	0.3798	0.3753
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4372	0.3887	0.3642	0.4289	0.4131	0.4951	0.4518	0.4553
	gpt2-medium	0.5147	0.3874	0.3753	0.4490	0.4148	0.4860	0.4456	0.5071
	mGPT	0.7682	0.7322	0.6571	0.7275	0.6993	0.3722	0.4151	0.3919
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.6726	0.5051	0.4342	0.7695	0.6230	0.3618	0.6033	0.6648
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.5439	0.4846	0.4907	0.5025	0.4830	0.4156	0.4845	0.3512
xlml-roberta-large	0.7099	0.5923	0.4626	0.7232	0.6210	0.3623	0.4792	0.6351	
vicuna-13b	bert-base-multilingual-cased	0.5322	0.5444	0.5417	0.5321	0.5429	0.4956	0.4570	0.4338
	electra-large-discriminator	0.4613	0.4599	0.4605	0.4708	0.4680	0.4852	0.4774	0.4705
	gpt2-medium	0.4400	0.4965	0.4809	0.5031	0.5477	0.6459	0.4519	0.5139
	mGPT	0.6592	0.6760	0.6616	0.6673	0.6765	0.5875	0.5462	0.5849
	mdeberta-v3-base	0.8342	0.8001	0.7582	0.8513	0.8957	0.6075	0.7289	0.9080
	roberta-large-openai-detector	0.4998	0.5137	0.5146	0.5088	0.5269	0.5206	0.4873	0.4461
xlml-roberta-large	0.8429	0.8318	0.7992	0.8220	0.8852	0.5332	0.5935	0.7620	

Table 18: Cross-generator performance of all detection models fine-tuned on the Russian language (evaluated per LLM).

Train Language	Train LLM	text-davinci-003	gpt-3.5-turbo	gpt-4	alpaca-lora-30b	vicuna-13b	llama-65b	opt-66b	opt-impl-max-1.3b
en	text-davinci-003	1.0000	0.9630	0.9091	0.9606	0.9153	-0.5403	-0.3397	-0.3932
	gpt-3.5-turbo	0.9630	1.0000	0.9755	0.9000	0.8939	-0.6074	-0.4288	-0.4835
	gpt-4	0.9091	0.9755	1.0000	0.8362	0.8697	-0.5739	-0.4265	-0.4911
	alpaca-lora-30b	0.9606	0.9000	0.8362	1.0000	0.9185	-0.4377	-0.2123	-0.2412
	vicuna-13b	0.9153	0.8939	0.8697	0.9185	1.0000	-0.2738	-0.0814	-0.1394
	llama-65b	-0.5403	-0.6074	-0.5739	-0.4377	-0.2738	1.0000	0.8306	0.8684
	opt-66b	-0.3397	-0.4288	-0.4265	-0.2123	-0.0814	0.8306	1.0000	0.9320
	opt-impl-max-1.3b	-0.3932	-0.4835	-0.4911	-0.2412	-0.1394	0.8684	0.9320	1.0000
es	text-davinci-003	1.0000	0.9559	0.8838	0.9107	0.9268	-0.6977	-0.6220	-0.6146
	gpt-3.5-turbo	0.9559	1.0000	0.9642	0.8045	0.8793	-0.7677	-0.7582	-0.7430
	gpt-4	0.8838	0.9642	1.0000	0.7110	0.8475	-0.7397	-0.7464	-0.7772
	alpaca-lora-30b	0.9107	0.8045	0.7110	1.0000	0.9211	-0.4645	-0.3431	-0.3439
	vicuna-13b	0.9268	0.8793	0.8475	0.9211	1.0000	-0.5080	-0.4104	-0.4309
	llama-65b	-0.6977	-0.7677	-0.7397	-0.4645	-0.5080	1.0000	0.8401	0.7872
	opt-66b	-0.6220	-0.7582	-0.7464	-0.3431	-0.4104	0.8401	1.0000	0.9164
	opt-impl-max-1.3b	-0.6146	-0.7430	-0.7772	-0.3439	-0.4309	0.7872	0.9164	1.0000
ru	text-davinci-003	1.0000	0.9575	0.9176	0.9459	0.9629	-0.3001	-0.1209	-0.1660
	gpt-3.5-turbo	0.9575	1.0000	0.9806	0.8830	0.9405	-0.3082	-0.2675	-0.2963
	gpt-4	0.9176	0.9806	1.0000	0.8255	0.9281	-0.2496	-0.2466	-0.3122
	alpaca-lora-30b	0.9459	0.8830	0.8255	1.0000	0.9460	-0.1665	0.0646	0.0440
	vicuna-13b	0.9629	0.9405	0.9281	0.9460	1.0000	-0.1229	0.0303	-0.0324
	llama-65b	-0.3001	-0.3082	-0.2496	-0.1665	-0.1229	1.0000	0.6193	0.4562
	opt-66b	-0.1209	-0.2675	-0.2466	0.0646	0.0303	0.6193	1.0000	0.8655
	opt-impl-max-1.3b	-0.1660	-0.2963	-0.3122	0.0440	-0.0324	0.4562	0.8655	1.0000

Table 19: The correlations between the macro average F1-score performance of the cross-generator on the English, Spanish, and Russian languages.

Train Language	Train LLM	text-davinci-003	gpt-3.5-turbo	gpt-4	alpaca-lora-30b	vicuna-13b	llama-65b	opt-66b	opt-impl-max-1.3b
en	text-davinci-003	0.6617 (± 0.14)	0.6860 (± 0.16)	0.6598 (± 0.15)	0.6182 (± 0.11)	0.6395 (± 0.12)	0.3917 (± 0.06)	0.4195 (± 0.07)	0.4185 (± 0.10)
	gpt-3.5-turbo	0.6643 (± 0.14)	0.7047 (± 0.17)	0.6891 (± 0.15)	0.6328 (± 0.11)	0.6609 (± 0.12)	0.4041 (± 0.06)	0.4083 (± 0.08)	0.3967 (± 0.07)
	gpt-4	0.5993 (± 0.11)	0.6641 (± 0.14)	0.6898 (± 0.16)	0.5517 (± 0.08)	0.5993 (± 0.09)	0.3942 (± 0.06)	0.3954 (± 0.06)	0.3687 (± 0.02)
	alpaca-lora-30b	0.6826 (± 0.13)	0.6876 (± 0.16)	0.6679 (± 0.16)	0.6753 (± 0.11)	0.6535 (± 0.12)	0.4519 (± 0.06)	0.4416 (± 0.06)	0.4562 (± 0.08)
	vicuna-13b	0.6488 (± 0.10)	0.6619 (± 0.15)	0.6517 (± 0.14)	0.6143 (± 0.09)	0.6476 (± 0.12)	0.4652 (± 0.05)	0.4620 (± 0.09)	0.4563 (± 0.13)
	llama-65b	0.4551 (± 0.08)	0.4466 (± 0.07)	0.4754 (± 0.06)	0.4640 (± 0.06)	0.5048 (± 0.07)	0.5713 (± 0.10)	0.5391 (± 0.07)	0.5542 (± 0.09)
	opt-66b	0.4925 (± 0.05)	0.4989 (± 0.06)	0.5366 (± 0.06)	0.4708 (± 0.02)	0.5483 (± 0.06)	0.6285 (± 0.08)	0.5587 (± 0.05)	0.5620 (± 0.08)
	opt-impl-max-1.3b	0.5614 (± 0.06)	0.5460 (± 0.07)	0.5430 (± 0.06)	0.5745 (± 0.07)	0.6196 (± 0.10)	0.6617 (± 0.10)	0.6280 (± 0.10)	0.6832 (± 0.12)
es	text-davinci-003	0.7718 (± 0.11)	0.7837 (± 0.14)	0.7114 (± 0.16)	0.6968 (± 0.09)	0.7294 (± 0.11)	0.4163 (± 0.04)	0.4246 (± 0.04)	0.4392 (± 0.10)
	gpt-3.5-turbo	0.7236 (± 0.13)	0.7791 (± 0.15)	0.7270 (± 0.15)	0.6585 (± 0.10)	0.7007 (± 0.11)	0.4144 (± 0.07)	0.3976 (± 0.03)	0.3919 (± 0.06)
	gpt-4	0.6631 (± 0.15)	0.7333 (± 0.16)	0.7503 (± 0.14)	0.5998 (± 0.11)	0.6668 (± 0.12)	0.4244 (± 0.05)	0.3917 (± 0.04)	0.3795 (± 0.05)
	alpaca-lora-30b	0.7414 (± 0.12)	0.7398 (± 0.13)	0.6540 (± 0.14)	0.7573 (± 0.11)	0.7128 (± 0.12)	0.5235 (± 0.06)	0.4818 (± 0.03)	0.5226 (± 0.08)
	vicuna-13b	0.7439 (± 0.11)	0.7713 (± 0.11)	0.7161 (± 0.12)	0.6959 (± 0.08)	0.7616 (± 0.09)	0.5375 (± 0.05)	0.4754 (± 0.04)	0.5260 (± 0.10)
	llama-65b	0.4788 (± 0.08)	0.4753 (± 0.09)	0.4877 (± 0.07)	0.5378 (± 0.06)	0.5702 (± 0.06)	0.7655 (± 0.08)	0.6233 (± 0.10)	0.6813 (± 0.13)
	opt-66b	0.5669 (± 0.06)	0.5156 (± 0.08)	0.5016 (± 0.08)	0.5901 (± 0.09)	0.6245 (± 0.07)	0.6707 (± 0.08)	0.6780 (± 0.10)	0.6968 (± 0.10)
	opt-impl-max-1.3b	0.4749 (± 0.10)	0.4367 (± 0.11)	0.4129 (± 0.10)	0.5335 (± 0.07)	0.5480 (± 0.06)	0.6275 (± 0.09)	0.6550 (± 0.10)	0.8191 (± 0.11)
ru	text-davinci-003	0.6325 (± 0.13)	0.5549 (± 0.16)	0.4914 (± 0.12)	0.6171 (± 0.15)	0.5626 (± 0.12)	0.4055 (± 0.06)	0.4656 (± 0.07)	0.4830 (± 0.13)
	gpt-3.5-turbo	0.6759 (± 0.21)	0.7272 (± 0.21)	0.7087 (± 0.21)	0.6492 (± 0.18)	0.6688 (± 0.20)	0.4152 (± 0.03)	0.4130 (± 0.04)	0.3937 (± 0.03)
	gpt-4	0.6449 (± 0.18)	0.6905 (± 0.19)	0.7013 (± 0.19)	0.6032 (± 0.13)	0.6353 (± 0.17)	0.4238 (± 0.04)	0.4186 (± 0.03)	0.3898 (± 0.05)
	alpaca-lora-30b	0.6520 (± 0.19)	0.6620 (± 0.16)	0.6284 (± 0.15)	0.6968 (± 0.17)	0.6417 (± 0.18)	0.5504 (± 0.06)	0.5275 (± 0.11)	0.5903 (± 0.17)
	vicuna-13b	0.6099 (± 0.17)	0.6175 (± 0.15)	0.6024 (± 0.14)	0.6222 (± 0.16)	0.6490 (± 0.18)	0.5536 (± 0.06)	0.5346 (± 0.10)	0.5884 (± 0.18)
	llama-65b	0.4663 (± 0.05)	0.4514 (± 0.03)	0.4730 (± 0.04)	0.5068 (± 0.07)	0.5212 (± 0.08)	0.6366 (± 0.10)	0.5697 (± 0.11)	0.5841 (± 0.13)
	opt-66b	0.4189 (± 0.05)	0.3754 (± 0.04)	0.3769 (± 0.04)	0.4698 (± 0.04)	0.4513 (± 0.03)	0.5742 (± 0.13)	0.6328 (± 0.13)	0.6938 (± 0.21)
	opt-impl-max-1.3b	0.4034 (± 0.09)	0.3773 (± 0.06)	0.3643 (± 0.05)	0.4413 (± 0.07)	0.4036 (± 0.06)	0.4374 (± 0.07)	0.5101 (± 0.05)	0.6612 (± 0.10)

Table 20: The mean and standard deviation between the macro average F1-score performance of the cross-generator on the English, Spanish, and Russian languages.